

74th Annual Meeting Program

TOWARD A SOCIOLOGY OF VIOLENCE

**August 9-11
2024**

Le Centre Sheraton Montréal Hotel
Montréal, Canada

Dr. Mary Bernstein
SSSP President
University of Connecticut

**Society for the
Study of Social Problems**
In Pursuit of Social Justice

Preliminary Program Schedule

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Thursday, August 8

11:45am – 4:45pm **Meeting**

Board of Directors Meeting I, 2023-24

Room: Salon 1

6:30pm – 7:30pm **Reception**

Arrival Meet & Greet Reception: Open to SSSP Registrants

Location: Ballroom Foyer

All meeting registrants are invited to the Arrival Meet & Greet Reception. Join us as we celebrate the opening of the 74th Annual Meeting. This social hour provides opportunities to renew past acquaintances, chat with old friends, and find a newcomer to befriend. New members and first-time meeting attendees are particularly encouraged to attend. A cash bar (subsidized by SSSP) and heavy hors d'oeuvres will be available.

Friday, August 9

8:30am – 10:10am **Meeting**

Council of Division Chairpersons, 2023-24 & 2024-25

Room: Salon 1

8:30am – 10:10am **Sessions**

THEMATIC

Session 001: Gender-Based Violence: Institutional Issues

Room: Drummond West

Sponsors: Crime and Justice
 Family
 Gender
 Sexual Behavior, Politics, and Communities

Organizer: Lloyd Klein, LaGuardia Community College

Presider: Cory Rowe, LaGuardia Community College, CUNY

Description:

This session offers an analysis of gender-based violence and individual attitudes as represented among incarcerated women,

state institution members, university settings, and police violence.

Papers:

“Campuses in Crisis: The Failure of Sexual Violence Policies and Procedures at Canadian Universities,” Elizabeth Quinlan, University of Saskatchewan, Andrea Quinlan, University of Waterloo and Curtis Fogel, Brock University

“My Brotherhood or My Brothers? Fraternities Navigate Organizational Change,” Anna K. Wood, University of Michigan

“Bringing it Home: Police-perpetrated Gender Violence and Legal Estrangement in Chicago,” Anna D. Fox, The University of Chicago

“From ‘Culture’ to Complicity: Investigating Responses to Gender Violence in a State Institution,” Jillian E. Sunderland, University of Toronto

“Empowering Transformation: Teaching Women in Prison Charged with Violent Crimes,” Cory Rowe, LaGuardia Community College, CUNY and Kathy Mora, John Jay College, CUNY

Session 002: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Teaching Institutional Ethnography

Room: Joyce

Sponsor: Institutional Ethnography

Organizers & Presiders/

Discussants: Eric Mykhalovskiy, York University
 Suzanne Vaughan, Professor Emeritus, Arizona State University

Description:

Institutional Ethnography (IE) is an important alternative sociology with a growing corpus of empirical and methodological writings produced by scholars across the globe. Writing and discourse specially on how to teach IE is far less common, despite its importance for the continued development of IE. As an approach that cuts against the grain of established sociology, IE can be difficult to teach and learn. This session invites speakers and participants to critically reflect on the challenges, possibilities, and future of teaching IE. Our aim is to create a context for sharing ideas, resources, and strategies that can strengthen teaching IE as an alternative sociology.

Papers:

“How Did Dorothy Teach? Reflections on a Memorable Day,” Marjorie DeVault, Professor Emeritus, Syracuse University

“Institutional Ethnography, Sociology, and Undergraduate Teaching,” Eric Mykhalovskiy, York University

“Introduction to Sociology Courses as Moments of First Exposures of Students to Institutional Ethnography: Potentials and Challenges,” Agnieszka Doll, University of British Columbia

“Pedagogue and Praxis in the Classroom: Using IE to Teach Undergraduate Students Critical Thinking,” Matthew J.P. Strang, York University

“Teaching and Learning Institutional Ethnography inside and outside the University,” Naomi E. Nichols, Trent University and Jayne Malenfant, McGill University

“Experiences of Teaching and Mentoring Institutional Ethnography,” Suzanne Vaughan, Professor Emeritus, Arizona State University

Session 003: Empowered People: Local Regeneration
Room: Hemon

Sponsor: Community Research and Development

Organizer & President: Paul Draus, University of Michigan-Dearborn

Description:

Using a combination of case studies, quantitative data analysis, ethnography and participatory action research, the papers in this session consider factors that contribute to increased or decreased civic engagement around local regeneration efforts, from the streets of Calgary to the alleys of Detroit, from the parishes of Southeast Louisiana to the homeless population of Portland, Oregon.

Papers:

“Long-term Resilience of Vulnerable Communities in Southeast Louisiana: An Interrogation of Disaster Capitalism and Gentrification,” Storm Wells, Loyola University New Orleans and Tulane University

“Identifying Supports for Unhoused Portlanders: A PAR Project,” Susan Halverson, Portland State University and Caleb Coder, Cultivate Initiatives

“The Intersection between Mastery, Community Engagement, and Perceived Neighborhood Quality,” Rachel E.M. Johnson and Amanda C. McGowan, Baylor University

“Opening Doors and Improving Lives: Merging Applied Sociology with a Bit of Neuroscience and Learning Science,” Marilyn L. Dyck, The Doorway and Jeffrey A. Will, University of North Florida Center for Community Initiatives

“Alley Alchemy: The Application of Urban Acupuncture in Detroit’s Neglected Neighborhoods,” Paul Draus, University of Michigan-Dearborn and Benjamin Gaydos, University of Michigan-Flint

Session 004: Inequalities and Abilities
Room: Jarry

Sponsors: Poverty, Class, and Inequality
Sport, Leisure, and the Body

Organizer & President: Annette M. Mackay, SUNY Oneonta

Description:

Over the past 4 or 5 decades, public policy has advanced the effort to include persons with disabilities into all aspects of social life. This session explores ongoing inequalities according to ability even after passing the Americans with Disabilities Act and Title IX legislation.

Papers:

“Belonging à la Muscle: The Unspoken Rule of Gay Men’s Pride Bodies,” Daniel Uy, University of Toronto

“Geographies of (Sporting) Islamophobia: The Impact of Mosque-based Sports Programs on the Movement Practices of Muslim Women in Canada,” Zeana Hamdonah, University of Toronto, Winner of the Sport, Leisure, and the Body Division’s Student Paper Competition

“How Discovery Rule Accelerates the Treadmill of Law,” Tanesha A. Thomas, Montclair State University

“The Lived Experiences of Incarcerated Transgender and Gender Nonconforming Adults: A Scoping Review,” Meechie Poston and Veronica Barrios, Miami University

“The Normate Circle and the Biopolitics of Trans Stigma,” Eden Dean Ellen Nay, Oklahoma State University, Winner of the Social Problems Theory Division’s Student Paper Competition

THEMATIC

Session 005: Violent Environments: Empire and Colonial Legacies
Room: Musset

Sponsors: Critical Race and Ethnic Study
Environment and Technology
Global

Organizer, Facilitator &

Discussant: Allison R. Madia, University of California, Los Angeles

Description:

This session’s papers discuss the violence of colonization and empire and the use of the environment as an agent of social change. “Environment” is broadly defined, extending beyond traditional understandings of “the environment.” Papers included in this session address historical and contemporary dynamics associated with empire and/or colonization with an emphasis on place-based ways of being and anti-colonial resistance to environmental violence.

Papers:

“Black Skin, White Asks: The Role of Emergency Managers in Carrying out the Flint Water Crisis,” Aaron C. Foote, Central Michigan University and Cedric de Leon, University of Massachusetts Amherst

“Setting the Context for Denver Police Shootings: Historical Racialized Violence,” Robert J. Durán, Texas A&M University

“Urban Renewal and the Imperial Spatial Imaginaries of Postwar Chicago,” Peter Kent-Stoll, University of Massachusetts Amherst

10:30am – 11:45am Plenary Session

PLENARY

Session 006: SSSP Business Meeting
Room: Ballroom Centre

Sponsor: Program Committee

Facilitator: Mary Bernstein, University of Connecticut

All members are invited to attend the SSSP Business Meeting for an update on the status and future of SSSP. Summary reports on the Society and its key activities this year will be given. In addition, thirty minutes will be allocated to a discussion in favor of or in opposition to all proposed resolutions. The meeting concludes with the traditional transfer of the gavel, marking the transition of duties from President Mary Bernstein to incoming President Rose M. Brewer.

11:50am – 12:25pm Plenary Session

PLENARY

Session 007: Town Hall: An Open Forum
Room: Ballroom Centre

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizers: Mary Bernstein, University of Connecticut
Rose M. Brewer, University of Minnesota

Presider: Mary Bernstein, University of Connecticut

Description:

As a social justice and member-driven organization, open communication is essential to ensure that SSSP continues to serve members. In addition, the Permanent Organization and Strategic Planning Committee is working on drafting SSSP’s mission statement, values statements, and plan of action for the future. Please join us for an open dialog to discuss these initiatives, the future of SSSP, fiscal realities, how SSSP communicates with members, and ways to enhance professional opportunities and connections.

Panelists:

Mary Bernstein, University of Connecticut

Rose M. Brewer, University of Minnesota

Anthony A. Peguero, Arizona State University

David J. Luke, University of Michigan-Flint

Elroi J. Windsor, University of West Georgia

Michele Smith Koontz, The Society for the Study of Social Problems

12:30pm – 2:10pm Meeting

Joseph B. Gittler Award Committee, 2023-24
Room: Salon 4

**12:30pm – 2:10pm Divisional Meetings
(Open to SSSP Members)**

Community Research and Development

Room: Ballroom West

Environment and Technology

Room: Ballroom West

Institutional Ethnography

Room: Salon 1

Youth, Aging, and the Life Course

Room: Ballroom West

12:30pm – 2:10pm Sessions

Session 008: Addressing the Mental Health Crisis in K-16
Room: Salon 5

Sponsors: Educational Problems
Society and Mental Health

Organizers: Douglas J. Engelman, University of North Carolina
Wilmington
Kyla Walters, Sonoma State University

Presider & Discussant: Maureen P. Hall, University of Massachusetts
Dartmouth

Description:

Authors explore dynamics and impacts of mental health that impact youth, especially related to the school experience.

Papers:

“The Paradox of Adversity: Analyzing the Effect of Adverse Childhood Experiences on First-generation Postsecondary Education Enrollment and Retention,” Daniel Noriega, Chapman University and Rashad Freeman, Indiana University Bloomington

“Inside the Classroom: How Does Internet Usage, Early School Day Routines, and Classroom Design Impact the Mental Health of Students?” Jacob R. Bahnick, University of North Carolina Wilmington, Winner of the Society and Mental Health Division’s Student Paper Competition

“Developing Trauma-informed Teachers: Cultivating Resilience in Educators through Mentorship,” Maureen P. Hall, University of Massachusetts Dartmouth

“Youth and Suicide in American Cinema: Silence and its Repercussions,” Alessandra Seggi, Villanova University

THEMATIC

Session 009: Bodies for Sale: Use of Humans and Animals for Entertainment

Room: Drummond West

Sponsors: Critical Race and Ethnic Study
Health, Health Policy, and Health Services
Social Problems Theory
Sport, Leisure, and the Body

Organizer & Presider: Michael O. Johnston, William Penn University

Description:

The concept of “body culture” appeared during the 20th century as an area of study that focused on the aesthetics and movement of the human body. The study of body culture provides a description and compares bodily practices as they exist in the larger context of culture and society (e.g., dance, play and game, outdoor activities, festivities, medical culture, working habits, gender and sexual culture, fashion, body decoration, as well as popular culture). The Frankfurt School of Critical Theory first saw the body (living and dead) as a commodity under capitalism.

This thematic session brings scholars together to talk about their research on commodification and use of human bodies (and the bodies of other animals) for entertainment.

Papers:

“‘The Devil and God Are Raging Inside’: Exploring Gender-based Violence in the Alternative/Indie Music Scene Subculture,” Katherine Kafonek, Stockton University, Joshua H. Stout, Illinois State University, Andrew C. Gray, Ball State University, Michael Thompson, Stockton University and Jennifer M. Ayerza, George Mason University

“Children’s Social Interaction, Digital Engagement, and Mental Health in the COVID Era: Social-technical Production and Reproduction of Disparity,” Yuying Shen, Liyun Wu and Carlene Turner, Norfolk State University

“Destorialisation: An Assault on Our Indigenous Bodies and its Traumatizing Intergenerational Effect upon Our Sentience,” Eli Anderson, Quantum Storyteller

“Reflections on White-passing Black Identity,” Edi Mucka, University of Central Florida

“The Real Costs of the Unreal: Deepfakes as Digital and Social Sexual Assault,” Liz Wilcox and Stephen Pfohl, Boston College

Session 010: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: I Choose You: What Constitutes Family in the 21st Century
Room: Drummond Centre

Sponsor: Family

Organizer & Presider/

Discussant: Monnica Gavin, Clark State College

Description:

The institution of family has undergone many changes in recent years with the increasing global acceptance of contemporary family structures. As we shift our understanding of what a family “looks like” in countries throughout the world, new forms are emerging. This session will examine the 21st century family in its diversity as we explore topics such as interracial partnering, LGBTQIA+ partnering and parenting, marital migration, and non-human animal family members.

Papers:

“‘They Had Baby Faces Just Like Me’: How East Asian Women Construct Racialized Masculinities,” Olivia Y. Hu, University of Pennsylvania

“Asian American Men’s Ethnically Heterogenous Inter-marriage Patterns and Racialized Masculinity,” Jess Lee, California Polytechnic State University

“Ecoexpansive Kinship: A Model for Expanding Conceptualizations of Family to Include Companion Animals,” Rachel M. Schmitz, Oklahoma State University, Heather A. Love, University of Alabama and Jennifer Tabler, University of Wyoming

“Good Brokers, Bad Migrants: Migration Industry and Immigrant Illegality,” Dasom Lee, University of California, San Diego

“Intensive Partnering: Gendered Partnership Aspiration and Household Inequality,” Yinan Wang, Harvard University

“Legality and Why It Matters: LGBTQ Parental Identity Construction and Experiences,” Allison Jendry James, Albion College

“Yes, Dear; Yes, Queer: Division of Household Labor among Queer Couples,” Ami Mariko Hood Frost, The University of Oklahoma, Honorable Mention in the Family Division’s Student Paper Competition

“‘Omo Iya’wusa’: Family Inheritance Feud, Communal Conflicts, and its Social Problem in Akure South Local Government, Ondo State, Nigeria,” Adejoke Rachael Adesida, Achievers University

SPECIAL

Session 011: Networking and Navigating at SSSP: Getting the Most Out of Conference Attendance

Room: Drummond East

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizer: Claire M. Renzetti, University of Kentucky

Facilitator: A. Javier Trevino, Wheaton College

Description:

This session is designed to welcome new participants to the Annual Meeting. Seasoned participants with varying years of meeting participation will share insights and tips on how to get the most out of this unique professional experience.

Panelists:

Elroi J. Windsor, University of West Georgia

David J. Luke, University of Michigan-Flint

Stephani Williams, Northern Arizona University

Foroogh Mohammadi, Acadia University

Adriana Leela Bohm, Delaware County Community College

Giovanna Follo, Wright State University-Lake Campus

A. Javier Trevino, Wheaton College

Session 012: PAPERS IN THE ROUND: Gender, Religion, and Social Control

Room: Ballroom West

Sponsors: Conflict, Social Action, and Change
Crime and Justice
Gender
Sexual Behavior, Politics, and Communities

Organizer: Rafia Javaid Mallick, Georgia State University

Description:

Embark on a thought-provoking journey as our conference session, "Gender, Religion, and Social Control," unfolds narratives that delve into the complex interplay between gender dynamics, religious influences, and societal control. This session features five compelling papers, an engaging and insightful session that transcends disciplinary boundaries, providing a holistic understanding of how gender, religion, and social control converge and influence various aspects of our societies. This conference session promises to spark discussions that challenge assumptions and foster a deeper understanding of the intricate dynamics shaping our cultural and religious landscapes.

Roundtable #1 Title: Gender, Religion, and Social Control

Presider: Melissa Maxey, University of Oklahoma

Papers:

"The Effects of Religiosity on Criminal Behavior during Adolescence and Adulthood," Shelby Brazes, Wilkes University

"Women, Revolution, and Cinema: A Cinematic Narrative of Women's Representation at Home before and after the 1979 Iranian Revolution," Pouya Morshedi, Memorial University of Newfoundland and Labrador

"Contemporary Perspectives on the Roles of Islamic Religious Education to Strengthen Women Empowerment," mansurni abadi, The National University of Malaysia and Nia Nur Pratiwi, Jenderal Soedirman University and Muhammadiyah Student University

"Navigating Cultural and Biblical Norms: Experiences of Young and Older Married Yoruba Women in Abusive Marriages," Abiodun O. Oyeboade Adeyombo, Federal Polytechnic, Offa

"Exploring the Pipeline from TERF to White Christian Nationalism," Kat Fuller, University of Nevada, Las Vegas

Session 013: The Sociology of Psychedelics

Room: Hemon

Sponsor: Drinking and Drugs

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Sarah Cullingham, Trent University

Description:

From medical trials to legally sanctioned therapies and a burgeoning commercial market, we are witnessing a marked shift in the use and availability of psychedelic substances across North America. In this session, authors will present research assembled under the broad theme of "the sociology of psychedelics." Paper topics include the impact of structural inequalities on mental health outcomes associated with psychedelic use, how psychedelic-assisted therapies may offer lessons for re-imagining our health care systems, the relationship between psychedelics and dominator culture, and how regulatory changes in Canada are potentially paving the way for a commercial market of psychedelic-assisted therapies in this country.

Papers:

"Diminished Psychedelic Returns on Distress: Gender and Education," sean m. vina, University of the Incarnate Word

"Dominator Culture: Violence, Ego, and the Role of Psychedelics," Fabio Felli and Kaitlin Pericak, North Carolina Wesleyan University

“Paradigm Lost: Epistemic and Ethical Concerns for Psychiatric Use of Psychedelics,” Olivia Marcus, New York University

“Special Access Program for Psychedelics: A Regulatory Passage to the Market,” Agnieszka Doll, University of British Columbia

Session 014: Structural Bias and Inequalities

Room: Jarry

Sponsor: Poverty, Class, and Inequality

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Annette M. Mackay, SUNY Oneonta

Description:

What are the structural foundations of inequality in modern society? This session explores the conceptualization of biases and injustice and examines the consequences through lived experiences of excluded and marginalized groups.

Papers:

“Voices of Combat Veterans: Perceptions, Needs, and Experiences,” Melissa Villarreal and Angel M. Burns, Grand Valley State University and Josh B. Jordan, Davenport University

“The Colonialist Racial Contract: Legalizing Structural Opportunities for Global Anti-blackness and Islamophobia,” Zaina Shams, University of Tennessee, Knoxville and Christopher Rogers, California State University, Sacramento

“Superficial Justice: Transition Problem in South Africa and the USA,” Patricia C. Agupusi, Worcester Polytechnic

“Pendulum Wandering between the House and the Street: The Experience of Violence between Women Rough Sleepers in Iran,” Atefeh Kaboli, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad and Simin Foroughzadeh, Iranian Academic Center for Education Culture and Research

THEMATIC

Session 015: Racism, Policing, and Policy Change

Room: Joyce

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizer: Raja Staggers-Hakim, University of Connecticut

Presiders: Raja Staggers-Hakim, University of Connecticut
Johnny Eric Williams, Trinity College

Description:

National policing practices, especially those strategies and tactics used in Black and Brown communities, require deep analysis and change. In an effort to build the knowledge base around best practices to establish fair and humane policing practices or to reinvent policies and practices around policing, this session will

critically examine policies and legislation proposed over the last decade in the United States and abroad. Panelists will address harmful police practices that target and terrorize communities of color, policy practices and tactics used by police that require change, and/or, policy options that have been proposed or adopted to eliminate harmful police practices.

Papers:

“Anti-Black and Blue: Neighborhood Identity and Local Racial Ideologies in Chicago’s Police Enclaves,” Anna D. Fox, The University of Chicago, Winner of the Crime and Juvenile Delinquency Division’s Student Paper Competition

“Color, Race, and Interactions with the Criminal Justice System beyond the Black-white Binary,” Kemi Johnson Pratt and Philip Q. Yang, Texas Woman’s University

“Institutional Violence: A Multiple Method Study on the Effects of Policing on the Mental Health of African Americans at a Mid-western City,” Robert L. Peralta, Dani Jauk-Ajamie and Juan Xi, The University of Akron

“Police Surveillance Technology and Emotions in the Bronx, New York,” Katherine Gregory, New York City College of Technology, CUNY, Mia Budescu, Martin J. Downing and Tailisha Gonzalez, Lehman College, CUNY

“The Relational Racialization of Docility and Danger: Examining How Cues of Categories Underpin Race Making in Police-civilian Encounters,” Darwin A. Baluran, Washington University in St. Louis

Session 016: Experiencing the Law

Room: Kafka

Sponsor: Law and Society

Organizers: Chiara Clio Packard, University of Wisconsin-Madison
Catherine Hastings, Macquarie University

Presider &

Discussant: Shaneya Nyasia Simmelkjaer, Syracuse University

Description:

The law affects people’s lives in a myriad of ways. This session examines how people experience the law, legal institutions, and legal practice. The papers explore the experiences of a variety of different people with different legal institutions, such as parents in family drug court, individuals on parole, family members of justice-involved individuals cosigning bail bonds, and tenants facing eviction and housing instability. Together, these presentations will draw us into the lives and on-the-ground experiences of individuals as they navigate and grapple with the consequences of legal practice and legal change.

Papers:

“They Can’t Keep Their Foot on Our Necks’: Carceral Citizenship, Parole Reform, and Disrupting Mass Incarceration,” Shaneya Nyasia Simmelkjaer and Winston J. Scott, Syracuse University and Emily NaPier Singletary, Unchained

“Reconceptualizing Eviction: Examining the Violent Dynamics against Tenants,” Minji Cho and Natalie J. Cholula, Portland State University, Honorable Mention in the Law and Society Division’s Student Paper Competition

“Community Experiences with COVID-19 Eviction Moratoriums in Florida,” Estefany Londono, University of Central Florida, Felicia O. Casanova and Kilan Ashad-Bishop, University of Miami, Zinzi Bailey, University of Minnesota and Elizabeth Strom, University of South Florida

“Staying in the Program: Family Drug Court Parent Perceptions,” Erik Matthew Wittrup, Michigan State University

THEMATIC

Session 017: Research Under Neoliberal Regimes: Peace, Human Rights, and Social Justice
Room: Musset

Sponsors: Program Committee
Transnational Initiatives Committee

Organizer: Ligaya Lindio McGovern, Emeritus Professor of Sociology, Indiana University Kokomo

Presider & Discussant: Gladys L. Acosta Vargas, UNICEF/UNWOMEN/ CEDAW (retired)

Description:

This session brings together papers that deal with broad issues relevant to peace, human rights, and social justice in the context of neoliberal regimes. Neoliberal globalization constructs regimes that impinge on people’s entitlement to human rights and social justice which are the foundations of peace. Social institutions articulate neoliberal policies that produce social inequalities. But people are also creative in asserting their agency in claiming their rights and human dignity. The papers deal with issues related to finance capital, educational disparity and race, refugee support systems, expressions of public sociology, and indigenous people’s resistance to coloniality and capitalist extractivism in the Global North & South. The session combined papers submitted to two closely related sessions.

Papers:

“Indigenous Women of the Global South Challenging Global Capitalism, Extractivism, and the Age of the Anthropocene,” Ligaya Lindio McGovern, Emeritus Professor of Sociology, Indiana University Kokomo

“Toward a More Spiritual Technology: Soundbath, a Back Door toward Acceptance of Indigenous Thinking?” Peter Brooks, Independent Scholar

“The Financialization of Human Shelter and Community-based Public Sociology,” David Jaffee, University of North Florida

“Beyond Enrollment and Retention Statistics at HBCUs: Unveiling the Motivations and Influences Shaping Student Attendance and Education,” Anas Askar and Anthony Jackson, Bowie State University

2:30pm – 4:10pm Meetings

Council of Division Chairpersons, 2023-24

Room: Salon 1

Permanent Organization and Strategic Planning Committee, 2023-24 & 2024-25

Room: Salon 4

2:30pm – 4:10pm Sessions

Session 018: Critical Analysis of Measurements of Poverty
Room: Salon 5

Sponsor: Poverty, Class, and Inequality

Organizer & Presider: Sarah E. Castillo, University of Tennessee

Discussant: Natasha P. Ellis, University of Tennessee, Knoxville

Description:

This session delves into the complexities and nuances of poverty measurement, critically examining the existing metrics, their strengths, and their limitations. The papers in this session explore innovative methodologies, challenge conventional wisdom, and propose more holistic or nuanced measures of poverty. Topics include, but are not limited to, income-based measures, multidimensional poverty indices, relative poverty, and the impact of social, political, and economic factors on poverty metrics. The session aims to foster a comprehensive understanding of how poverty is quantified and the implications of these measurements on policy-making and societal perceptions.

Papers:

“Alternative Foodways in Nashville: Complicating Food Desert Mapping,” Melissa Luong and Samantha B. Myers-Miller, Vanderbilt University

“Assessing the Landscape: Critiques and Insights into Chile’s Poverty Measurement through the National Survey of Socioeconomic Characterization (CASEN),” Rossana A. Diaz, University of Tennessee, Knoxville

“The Social Wallet: How Social Influence and Buy-in for Minorities Can Offer a Window into Policy for Systemic Equity,” Kayla Marshall, Engineer

“Wading through Credit Swamps: The Making of Diverse Consumer Credit Markets,” Asia Inez Bento, University of California, Irvine

THEMATIC

Session 019: Curricular Violence: White Supremacist Silencing in Education

Room: Drummond West

Sponsors: Crime and Justice
Critical Race and Ethnic Study
Educational Problems

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Miltonette Olivia Craig, Sam Houston State University

Description:

This session focuses on how U.S. classrooms have become a political target, as numerous cities and states have instituted bans on materials and lectures that cover topics such as diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI), critical race theory (CRT), gender and sexuality, and bias in the criminal legal system. Papers in this session will discuss the challenges that faculty across the U.S. have experienced due to such legislation that seeks to uphold white supremacy, stifle academic freedom, and silence teachings that focus on discrimination of marginalized groups and communities.

Papers:

“‘I Love that Mexican Households Are So Family Oriented’: Uncovering Gendered Parental Community Cultural Wealth in the Lives of Mexican-American Students,” Angeles Rubi Castorena, University of California, Irvine

“‘Making Whiteness Strange’: Displacing Whiteness through an Application of Racialized Organizational Theory in an Analysis of a Southwest School District,” Florence Emily Castillo, The University of Texas at Dallas

“Curricular Injustice: How Medical Educators Obscure Structural Racism in the Teaching of Social Inequalities to Medical Students,” Lauren Olsen, Temple University

“White Liberal Supremacy in Higher Education as Symbolic and Institutional Violence: Experiences, Strategies, and Solutions,” Angie Beeman, Baruch College, CUNY

SPECIAL

Session 020: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Agenda for Social Justice: Active Agents for the Future

Room: Drummond Centre

Sponsor: Justice 21 Committee

Organizer: Jason A. Smith, George Mason University

Presider/

Discussant: David C. Lane, Illinois State University

Description:

This session will feature a dynamic discussion with authors from the most recent *Agenda for Social Justice: Solutions 2024*, focused on actionable insights to a number of social problems in the United States. Policy recommendations and solutions will be at the heart of the discussion, as panelists engage with each other and the audience. The goal of the discussion is not an overview or synopsis of the authors’ work, but centering the idea of research and people as active agents which can help shape the future.

Papers:

“A Bold Policy Agenda for Improving Immigrant Healthcare Access in the U.S.,” Meredith Van Natta, University of California, Merced

“Gender-affirming Healthcare for Transgender and Gender Minority Youth,” Ashley C. Rondini, Franklin & Marshall College

“From Blame to Criminalization: Black Motherhood and Intimate Partner Violence,” Sarah Jane Brubaker, Virginia Commonwealth University

“Affordable Housing in America: A Matter of Availability, Access, and Accountability,” Jeanne Kimpel, Molloy University

“Shelter from the Storm: A Framework for Housing and Climate Justice,” Tony Samara, Right to the City Alliance

SPECIAL

Session 021: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Sociology on the Ropes: Recent Attacks on the Discipline has been moved to Saturday, August 10 from 12:30pm – 2:10pm Room: Salon 1

Session 022: PAPERS IN THE ROUND: Sexualities

Room: Ballroom West

Sponsor: Sexual Behavior, Politics, and Communities

Organizer: Hannah R. Regan, Flora Stone Mather Center for Women and Case Western Reserve University

Description:

This roundtable covers an array of topics in sexuality.

Roundtable #1 Title: Sexualities

Presider & Discussant: Hannah R. Regan, Flora Stone Mather Center for Women and Case Western Reserve University

Papers:

“You’re Hot, for an Asian!” Resistance and Desires in the Lives of Cisgender Sexually Nonconforming Pinays,” Veronica B. Salcedo, Georgia State University

“A Dual Case Study of Elite Sex Trafficking and Government Indifference,” Thomas Volscho, College of Staten Island, CUNY

“Forbidden Desires, Intersectional Inequalities: Class, Coming out Strategies and Parental Acceptance in Post-reform China,” Susanne Y.P. Choi, The Chinese University of Hong Kong

“Queering College Sports: LGBTQ+-inclusive Athletic Department Policies at U.S. Colleges and Universities,” Jonathan S. Coley and Gabby Gomez, Oklahoma State University, AJ Kurtz, and Anna Baeth, Athlete Ally

THEMATIC

Session 023: Alternatives to Policing

Room: Hemon

Sponsors: Community Research and Development
Drinking and Drugs
Health, Health Policy, and Health Services

Organizers: Keisha M. Muia, Portland State University
Paul Draus, University of Michigan-Dearborn

Presider & Discussant: Keisha M. Muia, Portland State University

Description:

This session explores alternatives to policing currently taking place in the United States.

Alternatives to policing includes any service in which behavioral health crises and public safety needs are addressed by trained community safety specialists rather than police. This may also include incorporating human services programs as opposed to exercising punitive practices.

Using police as the primary tool to address health and social issues such as mental illness, substance use, homelessness, and community violence has contributed to mass incarceration. This in turn causes individual as well as communal harm and incurs substantial costs. Investing in other programs and services would reduce costs and address the harms that are tied to the current model of responding to public safety concerns.

Papers:

“‘But Do They Have Their Rights?’ Informal Kinship Care, Custody Loss, and, Substance Use among Latinas in a Socioeconomically Disadvantaged Community,” Esmeralda Ramirez, University of Southern California, Jessica Frankeberger, University of California, San Diego, Alice Cepeda and Avelardo Valdez, University of Southern California

“Alternatives to Policing: What it is and Why it Matters,” Keisha M. Muia, Portland State University

“Examining Experiences of Non-police Responses to Mental Health Crisis,” Jenny K. Leigh, New York University

“What Happened after the Crisis? Comparing Post-year Arrest Outcomes between Law Enforcement and Clinical Service Responses,” Catherine Zettner, Kaitlyn Kok and Leonard Swanson, Wayne State University Center for Behavioral Health and Justice and Juliette Roddy, Northern Arizona University

THEMATIC

Session 024: Institutional Ethnographies of Everyday Experiences of State Violence

Room: Jarry

Sponsor: Institutional Ethnography

Organizers: Jayne Malenfant, McGill University
Helen Hudson, University of Ottawa

Presider & Discussant: Helen Hudson, University of Ottawa

Description:

This session will explore the social organization of everyday experiences of State Violence, informed by the work of Dorothy E. Smith.

Papers:

“‘It’s Literally Jail’: Carcerality in School Discipline,” Karlyn J. Gorski, The University of Chicago

“Child Protective Services: Policing, Prosecuting, and Punishing Parents,” Anna Rockhill, Portland State University

“The Intersectionality of Race, Culture, and Income on Oral Language and Literacy Practices in the Black Communities of Montreal,” Tanya Matthews, McGill University

“Topologies of Dispossession: An Exploration on Administrative Data and Reshaping of Racial Capitalist Systems on the Lives Crossover Youth,” Faith Mottahedi, Trent University

THEMATIC

Session 025: Teaching about Violence: How to Navigate Trust and Disclosure with Students

Room: Joyce

Sponsor: Teaching Social Problems

Organizers: Kathleen J. Fitzgerald, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
Alessandra Seggi, Villanova University

Presider: Kathleen J. Fitzgerald, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Description:

This session will cover a variety of topics and issues revolving around teaching about violence.

Papers:

“Teaching about American Society in Broken English,” Jinsun Yang, University of Oregon, Winner of the Teaching Social Problems Division’s Student Paper Competition

“Unveiling Gender Stereotypes in the Classroom: A Study on Teacher Awareness,” Rowena Enguito Bagongon, Northern Bukidnon State College

“When Only Some Violence Counts: Curricular Violence, Community Silence, and How Education Must Shift in Order to Heal,” Cami L. Touloukian, Teachers College, Columbia University and Uzma Chowdhury, Teachers College at Columbia University

“Using Trauma Informed Pedagogy to Teach about Sexual Assault on Campus,” Kathleen J. Fitzgerald, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

“Talking about Suicide through Film,” Alessandra Seggi, Villanova University

Session 026: Contingent/Precarious Work

Room: Kafka

Sponsor: Labor Studies

Organizers: Jacqueline M. Zalewski, West Chester University of Pennsylvania
Seth Kahn, West Chester University of Pennsylvania

Presider: Jacqueline M. Zalewski, West Chester University of Pennsylvania

Discussant: Seth Kahn, West Chester University of Pennsylvania

Description:

This session examines contingent and precarious work across a range of sites (human services; Amazon; sex work; multi-level marketing) and situates the conditions of precarity/contingency among a complex array of analytical schemes: late-stage neoliberal capital; professionalism and white-collar self-perception; global supply chains; and more.

Papers:

“Amazon, Global Supply Chains -- and Gig and Contingent Labor,” David A. Smith, University of California, Irvine

“Double Disadvantage? Nonstandard Work Forms and Job Quality in the US, 2002-2018,” Jeffrey C. Dixon, College of the Holy Cross and Andrew S. Fullerton, Oklahoma State University

“Privileged and Unprivileged Precarity: Multi-level Marketing as a Site of Non-standard Work in the New Economy,” Nicole Cochran, Temple University

“Risky Business: Sex Work as Precarious Work,” Quinn Maya Kinzer, University of Wisconsin-Madison

Session 027: The Neoliberal Nonprofit-Trapped in a Conundrum of Care

Room: Musset

Sponsor: Sociology and Social Welfare

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Bob Spires, University of Richmond

Description:

This session offers scholars and practitioners to engage in dialogue and present work on neoliberalism and its impact on today’s nonprofit. From New Public Management, to managerialism and marketing, we intend to explore why neoliberal pressures on nonprofits have not faded despite continuous failure of late-stage capitalism.

Papers:

“Civic Engagement and Socioeconomic Well-being: How Much Impact Does Financial Strain Have on Civic Action?” Rachel E.M. Johnson, Baylor University

“How Much Do We Help? The Colonial Legacies of Anti-rape Victim Advocacy,” Melinda Chen, The University of Oklahoma

“Overly Honest Research Methods: Exploring the Messiness of Community Based Participatory Action Research,” Jaime J. McCauley and Jennifer T. Mokos, Coastal Carolina University

“The Industrialization of Nonprofit Labor,” Andrew Schoeneman and Bob Spires, University of Richmond

Session 028: Decolonizing the Canon: Global South Scholarship and Countering Western Hegemony in Social Problems Theory and Research
Room: Lamartine

Sponsors: Conflict, Social Action, and Change
Global
Social Problems Theory

Organizers & Presiders: Faryal Razzaq, Karachi School of Business & Leadership
Korey Tillman, Northeastern University

Discussant: Korey Tillman, Northeastern University

Description:

The session is dedicated to shed light on the realities of social justice and social problem theory implications in the Global South, as mostly the social problem theories were developed in North America, and create a hegemony in research and thesis, which may have discounted the ground realities in global south.

Papers:

“Critical Phenomenology of Citizenship and Protest Spaces: Online Anti-immigration Movement Discourse in India,” Chetna Khandelwal, University of Calgary, Winner of the Global Division’s Student Paper Competition

“Gender-based Violence and Human Security in Conflict Zones: The Lived Experiences of Internally Displaced People from Zamboanga and Marawi,” Diana Therese M. Veloso, De La Salle University

“Why A Focus on Autonomous Social Science Traditions in the Global South Is Vital for Decolonizing Knowledge Production,” Caroline M. Schöpf and Ramon Guillermo, University of the Philippines Diliman

4:00pm – 6:00pm Meeting

Feminist Collective Meeting

Room: Ballroom Centre

Organizers: Mary Romero, Ranita Ray, Assata Zerai, Florence Emily Castillo, Beatriz Padilla

Description:

Informal meeting of an interdisciplinary group of feminist scholars of color and allies to discuss future of the collective.

4:15pm – 6:15pm Meeting

Board of Directors Meeting II, 2023-24

Room: Salon 1

4:30pm – 6:10pm

**Divisional Meetings
(Open to SSSP Members)**

Crime and Justice

Room: Ballroom West

Health, Health Policy, and Health Services

Room: Ballroom West

Labor Studies

Room: Ballroom West

Social Problems Theory

Room: Ballroom West

4:30pm – 6:10pm

Sessions

Session 029: Cross-Generational Sociological Lessons

Room: Salon 5

Sponsor: Youth, Aging, and the Life Course

Organizer &

Presider: Brittney Miles, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign

Description:

This panel will examine the critical insights we gain from looking across and between generations in the contexts of education, medicine, and rural communities in the United States and Nigeria. Specifically, this panel explores how resident doctors in Nigeria consider aging in place, Black place-making through historically Black K-12 schools, intersectional intergenerational social mobility through education among rural families of color, and how 1.5-generation immigrant youth navigate informational resources for college access. Together, these papers highlight how we learn from diverse populations to reveal layers of meaning-making across and between generations.

Papers:

“‘They Are Just More Approachable’: Immigrant Youth and the College Information Search,” Irina Chukhray, University of California, Davis

“A Journey beyond White Coats: Aging in Place Intention of Resident Doctors in South-west Nigeria,” Macellina Yinyinade Ijadunola, Olajumoke Zainab Kasaba, Christopher Oluwatosin Omokanye, Obinna Tony Adolalom, Ifeanyi Jude Epunam, Jeremiah Okuo and Eyiemi Toluwalase Akeju, Obafemi Awolowo University

“Everything is Changing: Cross-generational Placemaking and Black High Schools,” Kierra N. Toney, University of Cincinnati

“Phased Retirement and the Devaluation of Older Workers in Academia,” Wendy Simonds and Taylor Pope, Georgia State University

“The Rural View: Exploring Intergenerational Intersectional Experiences in Education and Social Mobility among Rural BIPOC Communities,” Alexis Grant-Panting, Texas Women’s University

THEMATIC

Session 030: Sex and Violence

Room: Drummond West

Sponsor: Sexual Behavior, Politics, and Communities

Organizer & Presider: alithia zamantakis, Northwestern University

Description:

This session will explore the relationship between sex/sexuality and violence, the violence of (hetero)sexism, and the intersections of sex, violence, colonialism, and white supremacy.

Papers:

“Antisemitism, Islamophobia, and Jewish Fear of Gendered Violence in Palestine/Israel,” Emily Schneider and Lillian Selznick, Northern Arizona University

“Appraisals of Childhood Sexual Experiences and Masculine Norms among Black and Latino Sexual Minority Men,” Ellen Benoit, North Jersey Community Research Initiative, Martin J. Downing, Lehman College, CUNY and Jason M. Dotson, Wellness with Jason Dotson, LLC

“Exploring Similarities and Differences between Bullying and Gender-based Violence: An Intersectional Narrative Review,” Sarah Jane Brubaker and Zehra Sahin Ilkorkor, Virginia Commonwealth University

“Linked Lives and Disclosures of Sexual Assault in the Electronic Health Record,” Alyssa J. Davis, Savannah Bastian, Olivia Wilborn and Laura Carpenter, Vanderbilt University

“Memory Storytelling of Aids and Black Gay Living,” K. L. Broad, University of Florida

Session 031: PAPERS IN THE ROUND: Critical Methods for Studying Law and Society

Room: Ballroom West

Sponsor: Law and Society

Organizer: Michael Branch, Hartwick College

Description:

This roundtable is a space meant to explore and develop critical methodological tools for studying the complex relationship between law, culture, and society.

Roundtable #1 Title: Methodological Reflections

Presider & Discussant: Michael Branch, Hartwick College

Papers:

“Critical Race Theory and Wrongful Convictions: A Methodological Approach,” Marco Antonio Lueras, University of Miami

“How United States’ Newspapers Frame and Weaponize Asylum and Undocumented Statuses in Key Moments of Trump and Biden’s Presidencies,” Lurissa Carbajal, Stephanie Geagea, Nargish Patwoary and Alycia Wright, Arizona State University

“Using the TV Series Blue Bloods to Teach about Ethics and the Law,” Stephani Williams, Northern Arizona University

“Virtual Law and Order: Navigating the Ordinary Affects and Cruel Optimisms of Video Games,” Michael Branch, Hartwick College

Session 032: Who Speaks for the Community? Complicating Power, Representation and Decision Making
Room: Hemon

Sponsor: Community Research and Development

Organizer, Presider & Discussant: Susan Halverson, Portland State University

Description:

Social science researchers likely all engage with communities in some way. But what does “community” actually mean? Who is included and excluded, and who participates? Who is considered a valid representative of the community? How is power distributed and used in communities? The papers in this session explore and complicate community power, representation, and decision-making in spatial/geographic, identity, and interest communities.

Papers:

“‘No One Can Tell Our Stories Like We Can’: The Ypsi Farmers and Gardeners Oral History Project,” Finn McLafferty Bell, University of Michigan-Dearborn, Omer Jean Winborn, Washtenaw African American Genealogical Society, Briana Hurt and Sasha Kindred, University of Michigan-Dearborn

“Seeking Advice: Navigating the Barriers of Public Participation for People with Disabilities,” Alfiya Battalova, Royal Roads University

“Civic Engagement in the Homeless Community: How the Homeless Are Left out of the Democratic Process, and What to Do about It,” Caitlin M. Krenn, New York University

“Community Power in Inclusionary Housing,” Susan Halverson, Portland State University

THEMATIC

Session 033: Understanding the Sociology of Violence in a Quebecois Context/Comprendre une "sociologie de la violence" dans un contexte québécois/
Room: Jarry

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizers &

Presiders: Eric Mykhalovskiy, York University
Jayne Malenfant, McGill University
Mitchell McLarnon, Concordia University

Description:

This session opens up an opportunity for SSSP participants to gain insights into the diverse approaches to social justice scholarship in Québec. It features social scientists and researcher activists who reflect on the unique historical and political context of social problems research in Québec. Drawing on their experiences and research, they explore the challenges of working on a range of social justice issues within and across languages, borders, and perspectives. The session will create a space for dialogue about what this year's Annual Meeting theme, "a sociology of violence" might mean to critical scholars, researchers, and activists in Québec, and how this interpretation relates to scholarship and activism in other parts of Canada and the United States.

Papers:

"Epistemological Terror: Québec and the Threat of Black Studies," Philippe Néméh-Nombré, Saint Paul University

"Languages and Epistemological Violence: Histories of HIV/AIDS and Montréal's Haitian Communities," Viviane Namaste, Concordia University

"Equity and Advocacy in University-community Collaborations: Supporting Montreal Social Movements through Community-based Action Research Networks," Alex Megelas, Concordia University

"Extended and Chosen Family: Lessons from Quebec on Experiential Knowledge, Peer Support, and Love as a Liberatory Practice for People from Care," Marcelle Partouche Gutierrez, National School of Public Administration

"In Search of Harmonious Coexistence alongside Suffering: Issues in Mediating Visible Homelessness in Public Spaces," Anick Desrosiers, McGill University

Session 034: Teaching Social Problems with a Transnational Perspective
Room: Joyce

Sponsors: Teaching Social Problems
Transnational Initiatives Committee

Organizers &

Presiders: Jinsun Yang, University of Oregon
Morena Tartari, Babes-Bolyai University

Description:

In the contemporary global landscape, most social issues extend beyond national borders, prompting us to adopt a transnational perspective that reexamines them through historical and geopolitical approaches. This session offers a platform for scholars, instructors, and activists to collaboratively explore the potential and challenges of integrating a transnational perspective into classroom discussions on social issues.

Papers:

"Embracing Open Educational Resources (OER) in Sociology: A Case Study of SUNY Oneonta's Department of Sociology," Gregory M. Fulkerson, Alexander R. Thomas, Elizabeth K. Seale, Kirsten Kemmerer, Brian M. Lowe, Lisa Curch, Ho Hon Leung and Ed Beck, SUNY Oneonta

"Exploring the Impact of Marginalized Identities on Teaching Inequality in Sociology: A Multifaceted Analysis of Political Discourse in the U.S.," Angela Vergara, University of Central Florida

"Intertwining the Significance of Critical Race Theory and the Sociology of Race and Ethnicity," Christine M. Capili, University of Oregon

"Teaching Health and the Media: A Transnational Perspective," A. Susana Ramirez, University of California, Merced

"Who Are You? Using Personal Storytelling to Teach Sociological Concepts," Monnica Gavin, Clark State College

Session 035: Global Health, Climate, Inequality and Environment I
Room: Kafka

Sponsors: Environment and Technology
Global
Health, Health Policy, and Health Services
Poverty, Class, and Inequality

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Clare E.B. Cannon, University of California, Davis
Description:

This session tackles issues related to global health, climate, inequality and the environment. It is one of two sessions on this topic.

Papers:

"Under What Conditions Are Ethnic Enclaves Beneficial for Health in Urban Areas? - A Conceptual Framework," Oluwaseun Temitope Emoruwa, University of Alabama at Birmingham

“Ready to Abandon Your Community?": Unsaid Analysis of Disaster Capitalism Impacts on Native Hawaiians Post Maui Wildfire," Sydney M. Shevat and Helen E. Wilds, University of Tennessee, Knoxville

“Environmental Risk and the Reorganization of Urban Inequality in the Late 19th and Early 20th Century," Jonathan Tollefson, Brown University, Winner of the Environment and Technology Division's Student Paper Competition

“A Feminist Community-Based Participatory Action Research Approach to Advance Climate Justice," Clare E. B. Cannon, University of California, Davis

THEMATIC

Session 036: Reckoning with Institutional Violence: Perspectives across Organizational Contexts
Room: Musset

Sponsor: Sociology and Social Welfare

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Julio A. Alicea, Rutgers University-Camden

Description:

This session seeks to examine how a range of organizations (i.e., social service organizations, government agencies, hospitals, schools, workplaces, etc.) create and reproduce inequality through institutional violence. Here institutional violence is understood as how policies, practices, and routines that contribute to forms of stratification and injustice within an organization. In focusing on institutional violence, this session calls attention to meso-level machinations of inequality that then resonate with and reinforce inequalities on micro and macro levels.

Papers:

“Methadone Access in Police Custody Healthcare as Denied Care: Strategies and Consequences of Detainment in Police Custody in England, UK," Stephanie Mulrine and Gethin Rees, Newcastle University

“Organizational Neglect: Unsympathetic Racial Crisis Response as Institutional Violence," Julio A. Alicea, Rutgers University-Camden

“Racial Equity in Homelessness Response: A Qualitative Study of Two Urban Communities," Molly K. Richard, Boston University

“Volatile Service Encounters: Tensions in the Service Triangle at Dollar General," Tracy L. Vargas, University of North Carolina at Pembroke

THEMATIC

Session 037: Culture in Conflict, Action, and Change I: Mobilization, Organizing, Resistance, and Politicization

Room: Lamartine

Sponsor: Conflict, Social Action, and Change

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: C. Michael Awsumb, Northwest Missouri State University

Description:

Papers in this session explore the ways symbolic and subjective factors (e.g., community-based culture, ideology, narrative, and trust) shape the experiences and outcomes of activist/organizer/movement mobilization, politicization, organization, and resistance.

Papers:

“Mobilizing Potential: Pathways to Engaged Citizenship," Sadie Dempsey, University of Wisconsin

“Barriers to Participation in Protest," Burrell Vann, San Diego State University

“Mobilizing Cultures, Community Action Toolkits, and Rules of Resistance against Crimes of the Powerful," C. Michael Awsumb, Northwest Missouri State University

“Patterns of Resistance, Solidarity, and Organization of People without Identity Documents in the Face of Poverty in Iran," Majid Fouladiyan and Zeinabalsadat Fatemiamin, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad

6:30pm – 7:30pm

Reception

Welcoming Reception: Open to SSSP Registrants

Location: Ballroom Foyer

All meeting registrants are invited to the Welcoming Reception. This social hour provides opportunities to renew past acquaintances, chat with old friends, and find a newcomer to befriend. New members and first-time meeting attendees are particularly encouraged to attend. A cash bar (subsidized by SSSP) and heavy hors d'oeuvres will be available.

7:45pm – 8:45pm

Student Social Hour

Student Social Hour: Open to SSSP Student Members

Location: Stanley-Hotel Bar

All student members are invited to attend the Student Social Hour. Complimentary beer, wine, and non-alcoholic beverages will be available.

Saturday, August 10

7:15am – 8:15am **New Member Breakfast**

New Member Breakfast
(Open to SSSP New Members and Invited Hosts)

Location: Ballroom West

8:30am – 10:10am **Meeting**

Anti-Harassment Committee, 2023-24 & 2024-25

Room: Kafka

8:30am – 10:10am **Sessions**

SPECIAL

Session 038: Beyond Outrage, What Do We Do Now? Peace, Reconciliation, and Global Conflict

Room: Salon 1

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizer: Joachim Savelsberg, University of Minnesota

Presider: Mary Bernstein, University of Connecticut

Description:

What can social science tell us about a way out of violent conflict? This panel presents data on mass violence and post-conflict situations in Rwanda, Sierra Leone, South Africa, and other contexts. Based on research on responses in the fields of law, education, and journalism, this panel draws broader lessons for a world, in which mass violence is increasingly common.

Panelists:

Jillian P. LaBranche, University of Minnesota

Chana Teeger, London School of Economics

Hollie Nyseth Nzitatira, The Ohio State University

j. Siguru Wahutu, New York University

SPECIAL

Session 039: How to Get Published: Learning the Language of Academic Writing

Room: Salon 5

Sponsors: Board of Directors Student Representatives Program Committee

Organizer & Presider: Foroogh Mohammadi, Acadia University

Description:

Academic publishing requires certain knowledge and understanding of the process that is not often crystal clear to graduate students and junior scholars. This panel's discussion

addresses the principles, challenges, and creative ways of academic writing and publishing. The session will guide you through the process of converting a draft seminar paper into a submission-ready journal article. The panelists include academics who are involved in academic journals and will reflect on their experiences on the other side of editorship and peer-review processes. This panel provides essential knowledge for graduate students and junior scholars who plan to publish in academic journals.

Panelists:

Lisa-Jo van den Scott, Memorial University of Newfoundland

Earl Wright II, Rhodes College

Annulla Linders, University of Cincinnati

Japonica Brown-Saracino, Boston University

Session 040: Who Speaks for the Community? Complicating Power, Representation and Decision Making II

Room: Drummond West

Sponsor: Community Research and Development

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Susan Halverson, Portland State University

Description:

Social science researchers likely all engage with communities in some way. But what does "community" actually mean? Who is included and excluded, and who participates? Who is considered a valid representative of the community? How is power distributed and used in communities? The papers in this session explore and complicate community power, representation, and decision-making in spatial/geographic, identity, and interest communities.

Papers:

"Restoring Dignity to Language Translations of the Jicarilla Apache: The Retranslation of Goddard Texts: A Restorative Justice-informed Research Collaboration," Mariann Shakan, University of New Mexico

"Unequal Participation: A Comparative Analysis of Urban Planning Processes in Two Rust Belt Cities," Athena Nicole Last, Jobs to Move America

"Bureaucratic Violence in Community Engagement: A 'For Us, by Us' Approach to Mitigating Harm in Community-university Partnerships," Sarah E. Stanlick, Worcester Polytechnic Institute, Gabriela Pereyra, Northeast Farmers of Color Land Trust and Katherine Foo, Worcester Polytechnic Institute

"The Person in Socially-engaged Scholarship: Social Change, Human Dignity, and Radical Personalist Analysis," Allison S. Reed, Washington University in St. Louis

Session 041: New Directions in Institutional Ethnography

Room: Drummond Centre

Sponsor: Institutional Ethnography

Organizer: Katherine E. Koralesky, University of British Columbia

Presider &

Discussant: Katherine Hardin, McGill University

Description:

This session features IE research with a focus on using IE in novel ways.

Papers:

“Institutional Ethnography and the Problem of Orthodoxy,” Eric Mykhalovskiy, York University

“New Journeys in Learning Institutional Ethnography: Building an International Community of Peer Mentorship,” Katerina Melino, University of Alberta, Benjamin Carroll, Queen's University, Claudia Collado-Quezada, University of Edinburgh, Alexa Ferdinands, Athabasca University, Mark Hardy, University of Edinburgh and Jeffrey Sabo, University of Ottawa

“Smartphone Apps and the Social Organization of ‘Going Out’ amidst Crises,” Colin Hastings, University of Waterloo

“Social Workers as Willful Subjects,” Hagit Sinai-Glazer, Tel Aviv University

Session 042: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Work Policies and the Family

Room: Drummond East

Sponsors: Family Labor Studies

Organizer & Presider/

Discussant: Monnica Gavin, Clark State College

Description:

The impact of societal policies on family dynamics is significant, and work policies can either aid or worsen issues within the family structure. Policies that are rooted in patriarchal systems can hinder the complete participation of women in the workforce. Furthermore, policies that do not provide adequate support for employees' families can lead to stress and subpar work performance. This session delves into the effects of work policies on the family dynamic, taking into account topics such as parental leave policies, telecommuting, parenthood in STEM fields, caregiving in higher education, artificial intelligence, and indigenous workers.

Papers:

“Artificial Intelligence and the New Divide: Perceptions, Preparedness, and the Future of Labor Market Inequality,” Dujin Park, Chungnam National University, Suhyoung Choi, Lanu Kim and June Jeon, Korea Advanced Institute of Science & Technology

“Exploring the Work of Women Faculty through the Lens of Caregiving: An Institutional Ethnography of Caregiving and Carereceiving in Higher Education,” Emily C. Schubert, Laura J. Parson and Fredricka R. Saunders, North Dakota State University

“Methods, Measures, and Money: Re-examining Parental Leave Policies’ Relationships to Earnings,” Brigid Cotter, University of Southern California

“Pima Cotton and the Gendered and Racialized Experiences of Indigenous Workers,” Allison R. Madia, University of California, Los Angeles

“STEM Work Hour Disparity Based on Sexual Orientation: Heterogeneity across Gender, Relationship Status, and Parenthood,” Jisu Park, The Pennsylvania State University

“Teleworking, Stress, and Work Conditions before the COVID-19 Pandemic,” Taylor D. Sumpster, University of Miami

“Tenure-track Confidential: An IE of Pre-tenure Women Faculty,” Laura J. Parson, North Dakota State University

SPECIAL

Session 043: Making the Most of Mentoring Opportunities
Room: Salon 7

Sponsors: Committee on Mentorship Program Committee

Organizer &

Presider: Ebonie L. Cunningham Stringer, Penn State Berks

Description:

Mentoring is a powerful practice that facilitates learning, development and growth in individuals and professions. Moreover, effective mentoring creates safe spaces to ask hard questions, acquire new knowledge and share experiences. Whether launching or advancing one's career, seeking personal development opportunities, or nurturing the desire to make meaningful connections with others, mentoring helps to foster belonging and creates more inclusive pathways to opportunity and success. This session features a panel of mentors and their mentees who will share their challenges and successes with mentoring, as well as their tips for how to make the most of mentoring opportunities. Panelists will discuss how both formal mentoring programs and informal mentoring relationships can serve as pathways to long-term collaboration and mutual support.

Panelists:

Glenn Muschert, Khalifa University

Michael O. Johnston, William Penn University

Faryal Razzaq, Karachi School of Business & Leadership

Sandra Lynn Barnes, Brown University

Ebonie L. Cunningham Stringer, Penn State Berks

THEMATIC

Session 044: Health Justice: Addressing Discrimination in Health and Health Care

Room: Hemon

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizer &

Presider: Raja Staggers-Hakim, University of Connecticut

Description:

Health justice issues are historical and political in nature. Health outcomes for communities of color and other marginalized groups require further attention by the general public and sociologists to fully achieve health equity. The current session considers longstanding and ongoing health and healthcare concerns that specifically affect people of color or groups that experience intersecting oppressions of race, gender, class, ability, sexuality, and religion. Specifically, panelists will address reproductive health and technology, discrimination in health care, Black maternal health outcomes, and the implications of gender in the conception of the sick role.

Papers:

“Beyond Motherhood: Exploring the Unmet Sexual and Reproductive Healthcare Needs in the Medicaid Landscape,” Elizabeth M. Anderson, Indiana University Bloomington, Winner of the Health, Health Policy, and Health Services Division’s Student Paper Competition

“Gendered Legitimacy in the Sick Role: A Survey Experiment of Gender-Typed Head Pain,” Caroline V. Brooks and Emily A. Ekl, Indiana University

“Healthcare Discrimination, Healthcare Avoidance, and Self-rated Health in a Sample of American Indians with Type 2 Diabetes,” Gabby Gomez and Kelley Sittner, Oklahoma State University and Crystal Greensky, Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health and Johns Hopkins Center for Indigenous Health

“Intersectional Dynamics in Black Maternal Health: A Qualitative Study of Gendered Racial Disparities in Maternal Care,” Carla Devonn Brailey and Brittany C. Slatton, Texas Southern University

“Sterile Couples and Access to New Reproductive Technology Services in Morocco: Social Inequality and Strategies of Resistance,” Bouchta Ezziani, Moroccan Center for Social Sciences

THEMATIC

Session 045: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Critical Perspectives on Law and Violence

Room: Jarry

Sponsors: Law and Society
Social Problems Theory

Organizers: Keith R. Johnson, Retired Scholar
Michael Branch, Hartwick College

*Presider/
Discussant:* Keith R. Johnson, Retired Scholar

Description:

This thematic session on Law and Violence presents new work on the boundaries of problematic social systems with a focus on the law. The presenters ask these questions: When does “stop and frisk” become “stop and sexually harass?” When does a prison become a nursing home for elderly prisoners? When do immigration laws interrupt family ties? When does human trafficking law make sex trafficking the priority? When does politics become violent?

Papers:

“Aging and Dying behind Bars: Prison Nursing Homes in the Era of U.S. Mass Incarceration,” Hannah L. Schwendeman, University of Minnesota, Twin Cities

“Extended Parental Separation: Examining the Harms of Immigration Policy on Mexican Immigrants,” Natalie J. Cholula, Portland State University

“Right-wing Extremist Violence and Government Impunity in Comparative Perspective,” Pamela Irving Jackson, Rhode Island College

“Stop and Sexual Assault?: How Terry Stops become Legally Authorized Sexual Violence,” Brandon Alston, The Ohio State University, Honorable Mention in the Law and Society Division’s Student Paper Competition

“What’s in a Frame? State Policymakers’ Conceptualization of Human Trafficking,” Alexis P. Tsoukalas, Florida Policy Institute; University of Central Florida

“‘I Still Can Feel the Sickness’: Withdrawal Experiences of People on Methadone Maintenance Treatment,” David Frank, Alexander S. Bennett, Luther Elliott and Charles M. Cleland, New York University

THEMATIC

Session 046: Unraveling the Complex Relationship between Poverty, Class, Inequality and Violence
Room: Joyce

Sponsor: Poverty, Class, and Inequality

Organizer: Sara Maani, University of Milan-Bicocca

Presider &

Discussant: Felicia Arriaga, Baruch College, CUNY

Description:

In this session, we invite papers that explore the intricate structures and dynamics of the systemic inequalities and injustices that perpetuate violence, particularly against marginalized communities. We particularly welcome a critical sociological lens that discusses the underpinnings of poverty, class stratification, and inequality, highlighting how these elements foster violence against the most vulnerable populations. Discussions that uncover the ways in which exploitation and oppression reproduce poverty and social inequalities, reinforcing multiple stigmas and heightened exposure to violence, are encouraged. We welcome a diverse array of perspectives and methodologies, ranging from empirical studies and theoretical frameworks to detailed case analyses.

Papers:

“Exploring the Relationship between Decision-making Method, Violence, and Inequality; Collective Decides against Social H.I.V.,” Shayan Morshedi, Memorial University of Newfoundland and Labrador

“Poverty, Inequality, and the School to Prison Pipeline,” Natasha P. Ellis, University of Tennessee, Knoxville

“Unveiling Intersectional Narratives of Minority Stress among Chicano Women via a Flexible Diary Study,” Felicia O. Casanova, University of Miami, Esmeralda Ramirez, University of Southern California, Melanie McKenna, University of Miami, Kapriskie Seide, Davidson College, Alice Cepeda, University of Southern California and Kathryn Nowotny, University of Miami

“Sheriffs Driving Policy: Associations and Influence,” Stephanie Avalos and Felicia Arriaga, Baruch College, CUNY

Session 047: Environmental Activism: Local to Global
Room: Lamartine

Sponsors: Conflict, Social Action, and Change
Environment and Technology

Organizer &

Presider: Kat Fuller, University of Nevada, Las Vegas

Description:

This session focuses on topics relating to the social research on environmental activism in this current age of dynamics, such as local community organizing, globalization, extractivism, and litigation, to name just a few. How are communities coalescing to respond to environmental injustices? How are activists responding to the increasing criminalization of protests? Not exclusive to research related to these questions, this session focuses on international perspectives that broadly address environmental activism and inform our understanding of the crucial issues pertaining to activism around environmental problems.

Papers:

“Humanist and Atheist Movements and Environmental Activism: International Discourses and Local Experiences,” Morena Tartari, Babes-Bolyai University and Hamide Elif Üzümcü, University of Padua

“Fighting at the Meso-level? Environmental Justice Narratives within a Leading Environmental Movement Organization, 1950s to Present,” Sam Castonguay, Washington State University

“Organizing Corporate Environmental Activism: The Green Growth Elite Countermovement in Canada’s Atlantic Provinces,” J. P. Sapinski and Lola Godin, Université de Moncton

“Indigenous Knowing Traditions for Environmental Futures: Indigenous Relationality, Intimacy of Ecologies, and Collective Reciprocity,” Doreen E. Martinez, Colorado State University

“Environmental Justice and Indigenous Feminisms in Oaxaca, Mexico: Linking Territory and Gender,” Alessandro Morosin, University of La Verne

10:30am – 12:10pm Meetings

Annual Review Committee of the Executive Officer, 2023-24

Room: Salon 6

Membership and Outreach Committee, 2023-24 & 2024-25

Room: Kafka

10:30am – 12:10pm Divisional Meetings

(Open to SSSP Members)

Conflict, Social Action, and Change

Room: Ballroom West

Family

Room: Ballroom West

Sexual Behavior, Politics, and Communities

Room: Ballroom West

10:30am – 12:10pm Sessions

THEMATIC

Session 048: Critical Perspectives on the Israeli-Palestinian Conflict

Room: Salon 1

Sponsor: Critical Race and Ethnic Study

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Amani M. Awwad, SUNY Canton

Description:

The discussion will focus on the contested realities of the Arab-Palestinian-Israeli conflict. How mainstream media covers the October 7th act of terrorism involving Hamas and the Israeli government. Further, the continued genocide in Gaza will be explored, specifically, how the world responded to these atrocities. The action of the settlers and the IDF soldiers in the occupied territories will be examined.

Papers:

“It’s Our Way to Tell the World That Nothing Can Stop Us’: Palestinian Parkour in Gaza as Decolonial Praxis and Embodied Freedom under Occupation,” Raiya Taha Thomure and Zeana Hamdonah, University of Toronto

“Birthright and Support for Israeli Violence among American Jews,” Emily Schneider and Lillian Selznick, Northern Arizona University

“Feeling Bad about Genocide: How Liberal Anti-Racism Enables State Violence,” Emily Schneider, Northern Arizona University

“Portrayal of Palestine in US Media: An Analysis through the Lens of Third World Narratives during the Israel-Hamas Conflict,” Srijana Karki, Texas A&M University-Corpus Christi and Juan Du, Huizhou University

THEMATIC

Session 049: Disability Embodiment: The Way Out of a System of Violence

Room: Drummond West

Sponsor: Disability

Organizers: Ben R. Sher, New York University Silver School of Social Work
Alan Santinele Martino, University of Calgary

Presider &

Discussant: Alan Santinele Martino, University of Calgary

Description:

This session delves into the interplay between disability, identity, and systemic violence, offering perspectives that challenge conventional narratives and advocate for radical inclusivity and

justice. Through a diverse array of papers, we explore the lived experiences and systemic barriers faced by marginalized communities across various contexts, illuminating paths towards empowerment and equity. Together, these papers underscore the necessity of dismantling systemic barriers and reimagining systems of care and justice to truly embody disability in a way that moves us out of a cycle of violence and towards a future of inclusivity and equity. This session calls for a collective reevaluation of our approaches to disability, urging participants to consider how intersectional identities shape experiences of violence and advocacy for change.

Papers:

“A Crip Perspective on Sexual Education for 2SLGBTQIA+ Individuals with Intellectual and/or Developmental Disabilities in Alberta, Canada,” Alan Santinele Martino and Thomas Tri, University of Calgary

“A Voice for the Voiceless Refugees with Disabilities and Language Divide in Terms of Accessing Braille and Rohingya-friendly Sign Language through an Inclusive Justice System,” Natasha Israt Kabir, Southern Illinois University

“Beyond Accommodations and Institutional Barriers: ‘Crippling’ Possibilities in Higher Education,” Alan Santinele Martino and Naomi Eastman, University of Calgary

“Mandatory Supporting as a Radical Ethic of Care: Supporting, Not Reporting, Black Disabled Mothers,” Siobhan Marie Pokorney, The Graduate Center, CUNY

Session 050: New Directions in Institutional Ethnography II

Room: Drummond Centre

Sponsor: Institutional Ethnography

Organizer: Katherine E. Koralesky, University of British Columbia

Presider &

Discussant: Katerina Melino, University of Alberta

Description:

This session features IE research with a focus on using IE in novel ways.

Papers:

“Gendered Organizations: Higher Education Practices Support Metaphorical Barriers,” Wendy Laminack Cash, Auburn University and Laura J. Parson, North Dakota State University

“Rise through the Cracks: Institutional Ethnography as Praxis for Adult Educators,” Katherine Hardin, McGill University

“Understanding the Gendered Experiences and Power Dynamics that Impact Work-life Balance for Women Faculty,” Fredricka R. Saunders, Laura J. Parson, Emily C. Schubert, Cailin M. Shovkoplyas, Lisa R. Arnold and Rajani Ganesh Pillai, North Dakota State University

“Using Archival Materials to Conduct an Institutional Ethnography of Prison: Analytic and Methodological Observations,” Helen Hudson, University of Ottawa, Winner of the Institutional Ethnography Division’s Student Paper Competition

THEMATIC

Session 051: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Guns and Gun Violence
Room: Drummond East

Sponsor: Crime and Justice

Organizers & Presiders/

Discussants: Christopher Dum, Kent State University
Matthew DeSesto, Emerson College

Description:

This critical dialogue addresses the uniquely American social problem of gun violence. The seven papers in this session draw on a variety of methodologies in their examination of guns and gun violence. During this session, 5 minutes will be focused on presenting each paper and the remainder of session will consist of a facilitated dialogue between authors and audience members. Through this format, all attendees will have the opportunity to engage with the topic of guns and gun violence, and partake in a joint effort to forge a path forward that addresses this important social problem.

Papers:

“Twenty-five Years Since the Columbine High School Shooting: How Race, Gender, and Individualistic Ideologies Contribute to the Normalization of School Shootings in American Culture,” Linda M. Waldron, Christopher Newport University

“QuantCrit Descriptive Analysis of School Shooting Events,” Natalia Brand and James E. Connell, Drexel University

“Aversion to Gun-owning Neighbors,” Justin L. Sola, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill and Justin T. Pickett, University at Albany

“The Effects of Youth Indirect Exposure to Community Firearm Violence by Neighborhood,” Rachel Elizabeth Colello, University of California, Irvine

“Threat Level Unknown: Ohioan’s Assessments of Potential Danger Regarding Permitted Concealed Carry,” Christopher Dum, Starr Solomon, Elias Nader and Megan Denny, Kent State University

“Pathways to Voluntary Gun Abandonment and Decreased Gun Desirability,” Mary Lee, University of California, Irvine

“Transforming Narratives of Gun Violence: Lessons from Research on a Community-engaged Learning Initiative,” Matthew DeSesto, Eric Gordon, Rachele Gardner and Dana Edell, Emerson College, Maridena Rojas, The Boston Project and Hanna Qiu, Emerson College

Session 052: PAPERS IN THE ROUND: Experiential Learning as a Way to Teach about Social Problems
Room: Ballroom West

Sponsors: Sociology and Social Welfare
Teaching Social Problems

Organizers: William D. Cabin, New York University Silver School of Social Work
Laurie J. Linhart, Des Moines Area Community College

Description:

The session will focus on innovative ways to use experiential learning to teach about social problems.

Roundtable #1 Title: Experiential Learning as a Way to Teach about Social Problems

Presider: Laurie J. Linhart, Des Moines Area Community College

Papers:

“Bringing Mutuality and Reciprocity into Focus: A Case Study on Sustaining University-community Partnerships,” Jessica Lucero, Utah State University and Lucas Martin, Bear River Association of Governments

“Discovering Hidden Paradigms in Our Syllabi,” Andy Plotkin, Behavioral-Scientists

“Experiential Learning Using Grant Proposals: A Reflection on Two Pilot Studies,” Janelle M. Pham, Oglethorpe University

“Geographic Interviews as an Experiential Method for Engaging Students in Place-based Assessment and Learning,” Danielle Maude Littman and Denae Cook, University of Utah

“Towards More Part Time Doctorate Degrees in Sociology,” Barbara Katz Rothman, The Graduate Center, CUNY

Session 053: Global Health, Climate, Inequality and Environment II
Room: Hemon

Sponsors: Environment and Technology
Global Health, Health Policy, and Health Services
Poverty, Class, and Inequality

Organizer &

Presider: Clare E.B. Cannon, University of California, Davis

Description:

This is a second session on global health, climate, inequality and the environment.

Papers:

“Corporate Corruption and Energy Transitions: Global Harm within a World-systems Framework,” Kimberly Ann Haliburda, University of Tennessee, Knoxville

“Conceptualizing ‘Just Transition’: A Comparative Historical Analysis of U.S. and German Cases,” Jeehyun Lee, Chonnam National University

“Limits on What Is Possible: Realities in Existing ‘Just Transition’ Politics,” Nadia Smiecinska, University of California, Davis

“Critical Climate Justice: Understanding How Cities Recognize and Redistribute Equity in Climate Action Planning,” Clare E.B. Cannon and Eric Chu, University of California, Davis and Asiya Natekal, University of California, Irvine

“Queer Political Culture in the Face of the Climate Crisis,” Cameron T. Whitley and Melanie M. Bowers, Western Washington University

Session 054: Social Problems in the Digital Age

Room: Jarry

Sponsor: Social Problems Theory

Organizer &

Presider: David C. Lane, Illinois State University

Description:

This session is centered on the intersection of changing technology and social problems activity.

Papers:

“Violence, Justice, or Love? Interpretative Frames and Cyber Dating Abuse in Three Chinese Societies,” Susanne Y.P. Choi, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Tangi Pui-chi Yip, Gender Research Center of The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hsiuhua Shen, National Tsing Hua University, Xiyang Wang, Beijing Normal University and Lynne Nakano, The Chinese University of Hong Kong

“Now Trending #Violence and #Truecrime: A Literature Review of Violence, Crime, and Social Media Discourse,” Kemi Johnson Pratt, Texas Woman's University

“Engaging an Engaged Audience: From Classroom Content to Critical Conversations in the Digital Age,” Wade P. Smith, Eastern Illinois University

“#Politics: Understanding Young People’s Political Engagement on Facebook Using Ordered Logistic Regression,” Clara Mey, University of Delaware

“Feeling Meritocracy? The Role of Affect in the Transmission of Meritocratic Beliefs on Social Media,” Chiara Osorio Krauter, Humboldt University of Berlin, Honorable Mention in the Sport, Leisure, and the Body Division’s Student Paper Competition

THEMATIC

Session 055: Youth, Violence, and Inequality

Room: Joyce

Sponsor: Youth, Aging, and the Life Course

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Brittney Miles, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign

Description:

This panel explores the relationship between youth, violence, and inequality across the institutional contexts of education and family. Specifically, this panel includes critical perspectives from LGBTQ+ youth, young women of color refugees, and parents of children with disabilities, as well as consider the impact of the father-child relationship and family violence. Together, these papers contribute to our understanding of violence while centering youth and inequality.

Papers:

“Exploring Adolescent Affect Regulation with Family Violence-Exposed Youth: The Phenomenology of Feeling Like You Are Going to ‘Lose It,’” Katherine Maurer, McGill University

“How Dads Matter: Paternal-adolescent Relationships and Juvenile Delinquency,” Hope E. Ousey and Andrew Wilczak, Wilkes University

“Rethinking Refugee Education: Animating War and Violence as Storywork by Newcomer Youth of Color,” Santanu Dutta, Pallavi Banerjee, Pratim Sengupta, Megha Sanyal and Chetna Khandelwal, University of Calgary

“Rural Texas LGBTQ+ Youth Experiences in Schools, Churches, and Community,” Nicole Kraus and Shanna Peebles, West Texas A&M University

Session 056: Gender and Work

Room: Lamartine

Sponsors: Gender
Labor Studies

Organizer: Tracy L. Vargas, University of North Carolina at Pembroke

Presider: Abigail Malick, University of North Carolina at Pembroke

Description:

This regular paper session is dedicated to the debate and analysis of gender relations, the organization of gender, and the gendering of organizations within the broad context of work. To examine the relationship between gender and labor, this session will cover a range of topics that examine gendered power relations, identities, and issues of inclusion and exclusion around the world.

Papers:

“Challenging Shea as Women’s Gold: Myth or Reality?” Idowu Alabi, Wayne State University and Samuel Hunter, America Shea Butter Institute

“Navigating Margins: Resistance Strategies among Muslim Women Workers in South Asia,” Priyanjali Mitra, The University of Chicago

“The Benefits of Intergenerational Co-residence: Reconsidering the Effects of Women’s Education on Their Housework Hours in Urban China,” Shuyin Liu, University of Massachusetts Amherst

“Undoing the STEM/Non-STEM Dichotomy: Exploring Women’s STEM Experiences and Binary Definitions of STEM Involvement,” Zora Haque and Manning Zhang, Brandeis University

“In Our Brothel, Pimps are Not Allowed’: Market Facilitation and the Realities of Brothel-based Sex Work,” Popy Begum, Saint Louis University

THEMATIC

Session 057: Feminist Abolitionism and Collective Resistance to State Control and Violence

Room: Musset

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Claire M. Renzetti, University of Kentucky

Description:

In this session, presenters, using a Feminist Abolitionist framework, will discuss how the neoliberal call for individual responsibility and accountability for criminal offenses magnifies harm through the ripple effects of state control and violence, especially in racially and economically marginalized communities. In doing so, presenters will implicitly or explicitly critique Carceral Feminism.

Papers:

“Abolitionist Origins: Radical Histories in Anti-violence Organizing,” Melinda Chen, The University of Oklahoma

“Abolitionism against Vigilantism: Resisting Carceral Norms in Anti-trafficking Efforts,” Corinne Schwarz, Oklahoma State University

“Abolition Feminism, Advocacy, and Anti-violence Activism: Imagining and Creating a Lifeworld to Resist the System,” Sarah Jane Brubaker, Virginia Commonwealth University

“When Protection is Unsafe: An Intersectional Analysis of Civil Protection Orders and the Carceral State,” Alesha Durfee, Saint Louis University

12:30pm – 2:10pm Meeting

Committee on Social Action, 2023-24 CANCELLED

12:30pm – 2:10pm Sessions

SPECIAL

Session 021: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Sociology on the Ropes: Recent Attacks on the Discipline
Room: Salon 1

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizer & Presider/

Discussant: R.A. Dello Buono, Manhattan College

Description:

The threat to sociology as a discipline is growing. Recent moves to dilute or remove course requirements for sociology seem intent on undoing the discipline’s capacity for encouraging critical thinking. Increasingly conservative-minded administrations in higher education are bending in the face of state and/or donor mandates to ideologically muzzle, downsize, merge or eliminate sociology departments and their faculty. The American Sociological Association (ASA) among other professional associations have cautiously weighed in on these attacks in various missives. What can associations like the SSSP do in the face of these attacks? How can scholar-activism be defended in the face of right-wing hostility? This dialogue seeks to explore these issues confronting sociology and other academic programs based in critical analysis and advocacy.

Papers:

“Fight the Power: Stopping State Attacks against Sociology,” Rose M. Brewer, University of Minnesota

“The Death of Sociology? Don’t Mourn, Organize!,” Corey Dolgon, Stonehill College

“‘It’s Trump’s Fault!’ and Other Ways to Avoid Responsibility,” Louis Edgar Esparza, California State University, Los Angeles

“Our Fight for Sociology is Part of Today’s Revolutionary Struggle,” Walda Katz-Fishman, League of Revolutionaries for a New America and Howard University

"Same Old Song, Much Larger Band: The New White Nationalist Attacks on Higher Education," Woody Doane, University of Hartford

"Countering Attacks on Sociology: The Precarious Nature of Building Scholar-Activists, Professional Associations and Universities Coalitions," Mary Romero, Professor Emerita, Arizona State University

"Sociology as Complicit in Chronic Mediocrity: The Fight to Maintain the Status Quo," David G. Embrick, University of Connecticut and Johnny Eric Williams, Trinity College

"What's Old is New Again: Academia and the Postliberal State," Nancy Naples, University of Connecticut

SPECIAL

Session 058: Publishing Tips from the Editors of *Social Problems*
Room: Salon 5

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizers: Michael A. Long, Oklahoma State University
Kelley Sittner, Oklahoma State University
Andrew S. Fullerton, Oklahoma State University
Rachel M. Schmitz, Oklahoma State University

Presider: Andrew S. Fullerton, Oklahoma State University

Description:

The publishing process can be confusing at times even for the seasoned scholar. In this session, the co-editors of *Social Problems* share their experiences as editors, authors, and reviewers and discuss the process of publishing in the journal.

Panelists:

Kelley Sittner, Oklahoma State University

Andrew S. Fullerton, Oklahoma State University

Michael A. Long, Oklahoma State University

Rachel M. Schmitz, Oklahoma State University

THEMATIC

Session 059: Criminalizing Vulnerable Populations
Room: Drummond West

Sponsors: Crime and Justice
Environment and Technology
Law and Society
Poverty, Class, and Inequality

Organizers: Marko Salvaggio, Tulane University
Miltonette Olivia Craig, Sam Houston State University

Presider: Marko Salvaggio, Tulane University

Description:

This session addresses the nexus between criminalization and marginalized people, and/or criminalization as it serves to produce marginality. For example, papers submitted to the session could pertain to the criminalization of unhoused people, the criminalization of reproductive choices, or the intersections between race, criminalization, and the incidence of environmental hazards. These are only a few of the possible angles that could be taken up in this session. We welcome submissions that analyze dynamics pertaining to vulnerability and criminalization in multiple ways.

Papers:

"Criminalizing Trauma: Trauma-informed Practices and Community-based Juvenile Justice Reforms," Kayla M. Martensen, Oregon State University

"Examining Policing Homelessness in a Redeveloping City," Stephanie Southworth and Sara Brallier, Coastal Carolina University

"Judicial System and Social Reproduction: A Panel Analysis of 22 Years of Penal Practice in Canadian Provinces," Mohamed Imoussaïne, National Institute of Scientific Research and Côté-Lussier Carolyn, Université du Québec - Institut national de la recherche scientifique

"Navigating the Invisibility/Hyper-visibility Paradox: Redemptive Generativity as a Means of Resisting Racial-criminal Stigma," Jamie J. Fader, Temple University

"Punitive Inertia: Anti-blackness and the Policing of Motion," Korey Tillman, Northeastern University

THEMATIC

Session 060: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Anti-Violence and Violence: Counter-hegemony from Subversive to Revolutionary
Room: Drummond East

Sponsors: Community Research and Development
Conflict, Social Action, and Change
Critical Race and Ethnic Study

Organizers: C. Michael Awsumb, Northwest Missouri State University
Watoii Rabii, Oakland University

Presider/

Discussant: Watoii Rabii, Oakland University

Description:

This session looks broadly at questions around the types of political praxis persons and groups use and/or may theoretically

be necessary in response to forms of violence, like racism, war, genocide, structural violence, etc. The session concept is engaging with question of “who gets to determine the “right” or “acceptable” way to resist your oppressor?”

Papers:

“Broken Bond or Resilient Threads: Understanding Social Cohesion in Black American Streets,” Abass Muhammed, University of Delaware, Winner of the Critical Race and Ethnic Studies Division’s Student Paper Competition

“Dystopian Dreams: Narratives of Social Control and the Techno-future,” Katarina M. McGuire, University of Tennessee, Knoxville

“Exploring the Effect of Video Literacy Program in Enhancing Emotional Intelligence Capabilities in Primary Schoolchildren to Develop Resilience to Extremism,” Faryal Razzaq, Karachi School of Business & Leadership, Sana Ashfaq, Islamabad Medical & Dental College, Muhammad Bin Ashfaq, Rawal Institute of Health Sciences and Glenn Muschert, Khalifa University

“Keeping Papua on Fire: Investigating How Pro-independence Papua Activist Express Antagonism, Hope, and Identity toward Indonesia on Social Media,” mansurni abadi, The National University of Malaysia

“Rediscovering Citta: Vignettes on Violence and Healing in Life and Commercial Yoga Spaces,” Brett Lesley Cumberbatch, University of Manitoba

“Resistance to Sexual Violence as Statecraft,” Melanie Brazzell, Harvard University

“The Reproduction of Colonial Violence in Humanizing and Peacebuilding Initiatives,” Emily Schneider, Northern Arizona University

THEMATIC

Session 061: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Womxn's Bodies as Sites of Statist Violence: A Critique of Imperialist, Heteropatriarchal Politics
Room: Salon 7

Sponsor: Gender

Organizers: Pallavi Banerjee, University of Calgary
Meghna Bhat, Independent Consultant & Scholar

*Presider/
Discussant:* Pallavi Banerjee, University of Calgary

Description:

The critical dialogue session invites researchers and practitioners to submit papers that discuss the mechanism through which state and institutions of the state seek to control and oppress bodies that are perceived feminine. The panel particularly invites dialogue that is anti-racist, anti-hetero-cis-patriarchal,

intersectional, decolonial and orients the field of gender away from normative ways of knowing.

Papers:

“From Violence to Victory: How Young Black People with Diverse Sexual Identities Experience Religion and Spirituality,” Sandra Lynn Barnes, Brown University

“Intersecting Liminalities: Controlling Pregnant Immigrant Bodies,” Zoë Chaetana Miller-Vedam, University of California, Irvine

“One Life: The Impact of China’s One Child Policy on Girls and Women in Society Today,” Jenny Athena Wong, Mothers Lead

“Resisting Across Borders: Iranian Diaspora Activists’ Struggles in Transnational Contexts,” Fateme Ejaredar, University of Calgary

“The Problem of Mononormativity: Disrupting Colonial and Imperial Conceptions of Family in the Canadian Government’s Pursuit of Gender Justice,” Pedrom Nasiri, University of Calgary

Session 062: PAPERS IN THE ROUND: Bodily Autonomy and Health
Room: Ballroom West

Sponsor: Health, Health Policy, and Health Services

Organizer: Virginia Kuulei Berndt, Texas A&M International University

Description:

Bodily autonomy in the realm of health and healthcare has inspired scholarly and activist work across a broad range of disciplinary and methodological approaches. As such, this interdisciplinary session includes intersectional research drawing from diverse methodological approaches including in-depth interviews, policy briefs, content analyses, and literature reviews. Topics in this section include abortion policy, technology and inequalities, eating disorder treatment and research, autonomy in long-term residential care, and prenatal care.

Roundtable #1 Title: Bodily Autonomy and Health

Presider: Yuying Shen, Norfolk State University

Papers:

“Bodily Autonomy and Abortion Policy in U.S. States,” Kelsey Johnson, Middle Tennessee State University

“Coercion in Care: Examining the Acceptability of the Use of Force in Long-term Residential Care,” MacGregor Goodman, University of Manitoba, Rachel Herron, Brandon University and Laura Funk, University of Manitoba

"Not by Accident: The Technological Production of Embodied Health Inequalities," Manning Zhang, Brandeis University

"Parallel Experiences of the Panopticon in the World of Eating Disorder Treatment and Research," Heather C. Pizzanello, Salve Regina University

"Prenatal Care at SEPs," Leticia Morales, University of Southern California Suzanne Dworak-Peck School of Social Work

Session 063: New Work in Social Problems Theory
Room: Jarry

Sponsor: Social Problems Theory

Organizer & Presider: Clara Mey, University of Delaware

Description:

This session explores new trends and developments in social problems theory.

Papers:

"Big White Elephant at the Ballot Box: Reckoning with the Suggestive Power of Trumpism," Stephen Pfohl, Boston College

"Hurt People Hurt People: Theorizing Liminal Complicity in the Reproduction of Inequality," Andrew J. Shapiro, The Graduate Center, CUNY, Honorable Mention in the Social Problems Theory Division's Student Paper Competition

"The Process of Managing Stigma for Those Bereaved by a Drug-related Death," Tim Chesnik, University of Delaware, Joshua H. Stout, Illinois State University and Benjamin Fleury-Steiner, University of Delaware

"Toward a Sociology of Facts," Joel Best, University of Delaware

"Understanding Motivation for Service Learning with Identity Theory," Anne A. Statham, University of Southern Indiana and Helen Rosenberg, University of Wisconsin-Parkside

Session 064: Student Mental Health on Campus: Who Isn't F*cking Crazy?
Room: Joyce

Sponsor: Society and Mental Health

Organizers: Douglas J. Engelman, University of North Carolina Wilmington
Stacey Kolomer, University of North Carolina Wilmington

Presider: Stacey Kolomer, University of North Carolina Wilmington

Discussant: Douglas J. Engelman, University of North Carolina Wilmington

Description:

An examination of the propensity of mental health issues on today's college and university campuses.

Papers:

"Family Relations and Mental Health: How Do Divorce, Single Parenthood, and Disconnected Extended Family Impact Mental Health?" Abigail Kozak, University of North Carolina Wilmington

"Recovery and Potential for Student Transformation: Fieldwork on Collegiate Recovery Programs," Samantha A. McIntyre, University of Tennessee, Knoxville

"The Consideration of Race in the Organization of Campus Mental Health Services," Hana Gebremariam, Temple University

Session 065: Teaching Sexualities in the Classroom and Community
Room: Lamartine

Sponsor: Sexual Behavior, Politics, and Communities

Organizer, Presider & Discussant: Janelle M. Pham, Oglethorpe University

Description:

Papers in this session explore the possibilities for community engagement and learning around issues and topics of sexuality, both within the classroom and beyond.

Papers:

"'I Do Like Sex A Lot': The Missing Discourse of Sexual Pleasure in Canadian Sex Education Programs and Curriculum for People Labelled/with Developmental Disability," Melissa L. Miller, University of Calgary

"Gen Z and Teaching Sexualities: Strategies for Education Students that 'Already Know'," Hannah R. Regan, Flora Stone Mather Center for Women and Case Western Reserve University

"Punishing or Healing? The Paradox of Title IX," Anna K. Wood, University of Michigan

"Sexual Violence Resource Centers as Allies in Primary Sexual Violence Prevention in Schools and Communities," Linnea Hjelm, University of Wisconsin-Madison and Ayden Prehara, RCC Sexual Violence Resource Center

Session 066: Doing Fieldwork in the Global South

Room: Musset

Sponsors: Program Committee
Transnational Initiatives Committee

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Debadatta Chakraborty, University of Massachusetts Amherst

Description:

This session includes critical reflections on doing ethnography in and from the global south. The five papers in this session address a range of key methodological, theoretical, ethical, and existential questions for ethnographers around positionality, risk, serendipity, affect, embodiment, subjective locations, power, violence, and their relationship to ethnographic witnessing, writing and knowledge production. The papers draw on a range of multi-sited ethnographic fieldwork experience of scholars in India, South Africa, Jamaica, Bangladesh, and Hong Kong. Overall, the session contributes to deeper questions on negotiation of intersectional identities for and by the ethnographers themselves in relation to the communities they are embedded in and the generative possibilities of such negotiations in exacerbating and mitigating colonial and gendered-racialized harms, risks, and violence.

Papers:

“Gender, Race, and Class as Resources in Global South Ethnography,” Annie Hikido, Colby College

“Serendipity or Structure? Reflections on Power, Privilege, and Pleasure during Fieldwork in Hyderabad, India,” Sneha Annavarapu, National University of Singapore

“‘Belly Pain’: Violence, Method, and Ethnographic Witnessing,” Sadiyah Malcolm, University of Michigan

“Gender, Caste, Class, and Positionality: Reflections on Intersectional Power and Its Interstices from Fieldwork in Bangladesh and India,” Debadatta Chakraborty and Md Sabur, University of Massachusetts Amherst

2:30pm – 4:10pm

Sessions

Session 067: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Living Wage and the Challenges of the Working and Nonworking Poor across Various Ethnic, Racial, and Migratory Profiles

Room: Salon 1

Sponsor: Poverty, Class, and Inequality

Organizer & Presider/

Discussant: Tracy L. Vargas, University of North Carolina at Pembroke

Description:

Work is typically heralded as a solution to poverty. Yet, for many workers, this is far from the truth. This Critical Dialogue highlights the struggles faced by workers in a global economy characterized by rising financial insecurity, precarity, and risk. Special attention will be given to disadvantaged groups, including women, racial minorities, and immigrants, who are more likely to find themselves living below the poverty line even while working. Panelists will discuss where individuals are situated in the labor market, what this means for their economic well-being, and how vulnerable populations can effectively challenge compounded inequality. We welcome a rich and active dialogue between audience members and panelists.

Papers:

“Balancing Work and Family Care in the Aftermath of COVID-19: Experiences of Women of Color and Immigrant Women in Detroit,” Anna Maria Santiago, Courtney M. Jones, Abigail Perrien, Jasmine Zavala Gonzalez and Yasmen Alsuraimi, Michigan State University

“Impossible Domestics: Black and African Descendent Domestic Workers Experiences of Antiracist Surveillance, Disposability, and Precarity during COVID-19,” Venus M. Green, University of Massachusetts Amherst

“Nuestro Trabajo Es Vida: Struggles at the Intersection of Productive and Reproductive Labor Among Migrant Latinas in the Pacific Northwest,” Lola Loustaunau, University of Wisconsin-Madison

“The Oppression and Resilience of Migrant Women in Morocco,” Isabelle E. Cole, School of International Training and Salve Regina University

“Toward a Living Wage in a Right to Work State,” Jon Shefner, University of Tennessee, Knoxville

“Working All the Time: Why Immigrant Venezuelans Can’t Get Ahead in Florida,” Alayne G. Unterberger, Florida Institute for Community Studies

SPECIAL

Session 068: On the Market: Strategies for Landing a Job

Room: Salon 5

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizer &

Presider: Tsedale M. Melaku, Baruch College

Description:

In this session, our panelists will share their experiences applying for jobs and hiring for various positions inside and outside of higher education. This session is intended to help you improve your chances of getting a job, whether inside academia (e.g., post-doc, balanced, research, or teaching-focused positions) or

outside of the academy (e.g., non-profits, advocacy, foundations, Think tanks). We would like this session to be an immersive experience, where we hope that session attendees will include individuals who were on the job market this past year and are willing to share their experiences with others. Graduate students a year or more away from searching for a position are encouraged to attend.

Panelists:

Adriana Leela Bohm, Delaware County Community College

Kristen M. Budd, The Sentencing Project

Erica Chito Childs, Hunter College, CUNY

Tsedale M. Melaku, Baruch College

Elroi J. Windsor, University of West Georgia

THEMATIC

Session 069: Gender-Based Violence: Perceptions and Applications

Room: Drummond West

Sponsors: Crime and Justice
Family
Gender
Sexual Behavior, Politics, and Communities

Organizer &

Presider: Lloyd Klein, LaGuardia Community College

Description:

This session examines the issue of gender-based violence through the application of specific analysis offered in five distinct papers. Topics covered include gender-based violence in Federal insurrection, Prostitution, cultural aspects of country music, digital evidence in sexual assault, and victim typology in sexual assault cases.

Papers:

“No Victim Is Ideal: Investigating the Influence of Perceptions of Ideal Victim Types on the Presence of SAMFEs in Sexual Assault Cases,” Alyssa J. Davis, Vanderbilt University

“Not Safe at Work, Not Safe at Home: Sexual Vulnerability in Military Spaces,” Stephanie Bonnes, University of New Haven

“Victims on Trial? The Role of Digital Evidence in Sexual Assault Proceedings,” Anna Gjika, SUNY New Paltz

“Experience of Violence Perception among Iranian Prostitutes and Their Strategies in Confronting Violence,” Majid Fouladiyan and Atefeh Kaboli, Ferdowsi University of Mashhad and Fateme Noei Teymori, Azad University

“Anti-violence Work in Transition: From Radical Feminism to Picket Lines,” Elizabeth Quinlan, University of Saskatchewan

Session 070: Structural Determinants of Health and Legal Needs

Room: Drummond Centre

Sponsors: Health, Health Policy, and Health Services
Law and Society
Sociology and Social Welfare

Organizer: William D. Cabin, New York University Silver School of Social Work

Presider: Justin R. Huft, University of California, Riverside

Description:

The papers in this session will address the relationship between structural determinants of health and legal needs.

Papers:

“Assessing the Mitigating Effects of Social Capital Infrastructure on the Associations between Extreme Heat, Rurality, Older Age Structures, and Physical and Mental Health Outcomes,” Gregory M. Fulkerson and Alexander R. Thomas, SUNY Oneonta

“Belief and Wellbeing: Evaluating Health Outcomes in Religious and Secular Hospitals in California,” Justin R. Huft, University of California, Riverside and Katrina I. Guardino, Duke University School of Medicine

“Fight, Flight, Freeze: How Access to Support Shapes Tenant Responses to Eviction,” Natalie J. Cholula, Alex Farrington and Lisa K. Bates, Portland State University

“IEPs and 504 Plans Creating Apathy or Progress within Chicago Public Schools amongst Children and Adolescents with Mental Health Diagnoses,” Rodney Allen, Loyola University Chicago

“Making the Connections across the Health Care Continuum: Assessing the Impact of the JaxCareConnect Community Based Health Care Consortium,” Jeffrey A. Will and Tracy Milligan, University of North Florida Center for Community Initiatives

Session 071: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Decolonizing the Academy using Institutional Ethnography and Other Approaches: From Theory to Praxis

Room: Drummond East

Sponsors: Community Research and Development
Critical Race and Ethnic Study
Global
Institutional Ethnography

Organizers: Angela Fillingim, San Francisco State University
Urmitapa Dutta, University of Massachusetts Lowell

Presider/

Discussant: Molly Clark-Barol, University of Wisconsin-Madison

Description:

This critical dialogue session dives into the complexities of decolonizing academic spaces, methodologies, and epistemologies. The papers will showcase how activist scholars center and attend to structurally marginalized voices in pursuit of epistemic justice. Employing anti-colonial, intersectional, and transnational lenses, they interrogate dominant knowledge systems while exploring the liberatory potential of diverse onto-epistemologies and research methodologies. Beyond critique, this critical session seeks actionable pathways, bridging the gap between theory and praxis to dismantle colonial legacies within academia and beyond. Join us as we connect ideas with action to co-create more just and pluriversal ecologies of knowledge.

Papers:

“Black Agency, Racial Imperialism, and the Creation of a Racial State – the Case of Haiti,” Rodney D. Coates, Miami University

“Ethnography, CBPR, and Theory: Tensions in Sociological Research as Liberatory Praxis,” Molly Clark-Barol, University of Wisconsin-Madison

“Filling in the Blanks: South to South Exchanges of Blackness, (Re)Shifting Research as Resistance, and (Re)Negotiations of Difference in the Diaspora,” Masonya J. Bennett, Kennesaw State University

“Intersectionality in Institutional Ethnography,” Dara Gordon, University of Toronto

“Understanding Justice, Equity, Accessibility, Diversity, and Inclusion (JEADI) from Perspective of Unveiled Histories,” Assata Zerai, University of New Mexico

“What and Who’s Research Is ‘Real’: The Role of Qualitative Social Scientists within Medical Institutions,” Melinda Leigh Maconi, Carley Geiss and Hayden J. Fulton, Moffitt Cancer Center

SPECIAL

Session 072: Author Meets Critics: *Murder Town, USA: Homicide, Structural Violence, and Activism in Wilmington* by Yasser Arafat Payne, Brooklynn K. Hitchens, & Darryl L. Chambers, Rutgers University Press, 2023
Room: Salon 7

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizer &

Presider: Claire M. Renzetti, University of Kentucky

Description:

In their book, *Murder Town, USA: Homicide, Structural Violence, and Activism in Wilmington*, authors Yasser Payne, Brooklynn Hitchens, and Darryl Chambers, present their ethnographic study of the relationship between structural opportunity and violence in the city of Wilmington, Delaware. Through their engagement with city residents who were formerly involved with street activities and/or the criminal justice system, the authors provide a radical reconceptualization of violence in low-income Black communities, showing how involvement in violence and crime is a logical, “resilient” response to the perverse context of structural inequality. The authors will be joined by a panel of scholars who will engage in an insightful discussion of this important work.

Authors: Yasser Arafat Payne, University of Delaware
Brooklynn K. Hitchens, University of Maryland
Darryl L. Chambers, Center for Structural Equity and University of Delaware

Critics:

Claire M. Renzetti, University of Kentucky

Jamie J. Fader, Temple University

Anthony A. Peguero, Arizona State University

Louis Edgar Esparza, California State University, Los Angeles

Robert L. Peralta, The University of Akron

Session 073: PAPERS IN THE ROUND: Educators at Work
Room: Ballroom West

Sponsor: Educational Problems

Organizer: Kyla Walters, Sonoma State University

Description:

Authors consider theoretical and applied approaches to potential impacts, or even transformation of students and workers through educational praxis.

Roundtable #1 Title: Curricular Interventions

Presider: Jacqueline M. Zalewski, West Chester University of Pennsylvania

Papers:

“Interfacing an Indigenous Curriculum with the Modern American University,” Peter Brooks, Independent Scholar

“Theorizing Sanctuary Classrooms: Reimagining Classroom Spaces through an Exploration of Sanctuary Practices, Educational State Violence, and Abolitionist Teaching,” Mariaeloina Carambo, Drexel University

“Online Education: Styles and Approaches to Instruction by Gender and Experience,” Whitney DeCamp and Brian Horvitz, Western Michigan University

“Incorporating Career Readiness into Curriculum through Research, Application, and Intentionality,” Stephani Williams, Christine Arazan, Michael Costelloe and Madison Heck, Northern Arizona University

“Encouraging Productive Behavior in Student Teams with Interventions - Part II,” Jacqueline M. Zalewski, West Chester University of Pennsylvania and Susan Brudvig, Northern Kentucky University

Roundtable #2 Title: Labor, Education, and Inequality

Presider: Amanda J. Brockman, Northern Kentucky University

Papers:

“Teachers’ Class in the Classroom: Trends in the Socioeconomic Background of Teachers over the Last 50 Years,” Matthew Erkenbrack, University of California, Irvine

“Revitalizing the Role of Relative Deprivation: An Analysis of Contemporary Teacher Protest Strike Emergence,” Amanda J. Brockman, Northern Kentucky University

“Research and Learning Model of Union Education,” Jelger A. Kalmijn, California State University, San Marcos

“Gender, Care, and Bargaining for the Common Good,” John O’Connor and Christina Barmon, Central Connecticut State University

“From Rise and Grind to Acting Your Wage: An Analysis of Changing U.S. Workplace Attitudes,” Erica Mildner, University of British Columbia

Session 074: PAPERS IN THE ROUND: Teaching about Environmental Social Problems
Room: Ballroom West

Sponsors: Environment and Technology
Teaching Social Problems

Organizers: Angus A. Nurse, Anglia Ruskin University and Nottingham Trent University
Morena Tartari, Babes-Bolyai University

Description:

This session, organized as a session for “papers in the round,” explores the challenges and opportunities that relate to the teaching of environmental problems.

The session takes a broad view on environmental problems and includes papers on teaching climate justice and on methods and strategies for teaching environmental justice. It also includes papers that discuss the teaching of environmental social

problems through the use of research results and a discussion on how to develop *Ecopedagogy*, considering the specific pedagogical challenges and considerations inherent to teaching environmental social problems.

The organizers envision robust conversations pertaining to the many facets of teaching about environmental issues.

Roundtable #1 Title: Teaching About Environmental Social Problems

Presiders: Angus A. Nurse, Anglia Ruskin University and Nottingham Trent University
Morena Tartari, Babes-Bolyai University

Discussant: Angus A. Nurse, Anglia Ruskin University and Nottingham Trent University

Papers:

“Ecopedagogy: A Framework for Countering ‘Post-truth,’ ‘Anti-woke,’ and Individualistic Politics in the Classroom,” Lauren Eastwood, SUNY, Plattsburgh

“Teaching Climate Justice: A Research Agenda,” Angus A. Nurse, Anglia Ruskin University and Nottingham Trent University

“Teaching Environmental Justice: Methods and Strategies for Social Work Education,” Sara E. Strayer, Alliant International University and Stephen W. Stoeffler, Kutztown University

“Teaching about Environmental Social Problems through First-hand Research Results: Strategies to Prepare Tools and Presentations for Students and Professionals,” Morena Tartari, Babes-Bolyai University and Hamide Elif Üzümcü, University of Padua

Session 075: Understanding Stigma and Responses to Drug Use
Room: Hemon

Sponsor: Drinking and Drugs

Organizers: Juliette Roddy, Northern Arizona University
Dina Perrone, California State University, Long Beach
David Frank, New York University

Presider: Dina Perrone, California State University, Long Beach

Description:

Understanding how stigma impacts the treatment of people who use drugs.

Papers:

“Substance Use, Stigma, and Using Research to Inform Community Response,” Simon Purdy, SUNY Delhi

“Getting Sober with Satan: A Qualitative Observation of the Satanic Temple Sober Faction,” Maryanne Diaz and Kalani Lopez, California State University, Long Beach

“‘Harm Reduction Policies Are Great.... but Those Drug Users Are Always Trying to Get One over on You’: History, Structural Stigma and Violence, and the Limits of Harm Reduction Expansion,” Alexander S. Bennett, New York University

“Using Mobile Technology to Identify and Respond to Critical Gaps in Harm Reduction Knowledge and Access to Resources among PWID: Results of a Pilot Study,” Honoria Guarino and Seanna Pratt, CUNY School of Public Health, Emily Kiernan and Sascha Garrey, Independent Researcher and Pedro Mateu-Gelabert, CUNY School of Public Health

“Crime and Policing around Cannabis Dispensaries in Seattle,” Joshua Chanin and Burrell Vann, San Diego State University

Session 076: Race, Class, Gender, and Mental Health

Room: Joyce

Sponsor: Society and Mental Health

Organizer: Alex Trillo, Saint Peter’s University

Presiders: Alex Trillo, Saint Peter’s University
Giovani Burgos, Adelphi University

Description:

Race, Class, Gender, and Mental Health

Papers:

“‘I Read Quite a Bit, and That Brings Me in a lot of Escapist-based Joy’: The Value of Asking about Joy among Black Transgender and Nonbinary Young Adults in Florida,” Courtney Marcia Gardner, Shannon K. Carter and Lindsay A. Taliaferro, University of Central Florida

“Differences in Mental Health Outcomes for an Exclusively LGBTQ+ Sample in Oklahoma,” Eden Dean Ellen Nay and Kelley Sittner, Oklahoma State University

“Generating the Troubled Teen: A Content Analysis of the Troubled Teen Industry’s Recruitment Tactics,” Annie McDonnell, The George Washington University

“Mental Health and Health-seeking Behaviors amongst Married U.S. and Foreign-born Black Populations,” Tia M. Dickerson and Dana J. McCalla, Howard University

“Psychotic White Men and Bipolar Black Women? Racialized and Gendered Implications of Mental Health Terminology,” Amy L. Johnson, Lehigh University

THEMATIC

Session 077: Culture in Conflict, Action, and Change II: Narrative, Community, Discourse, and Identity

Room: Musset

Sponsor: Conflict, Social Action, and Change

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: C. Michael Awsumb, Northwest Missouri State University

Description:

Papers in this session explore the roles and effects of narrative, community, discourse, and identity in experience of, mobilization against, and resistance to victimization, violence, and marginalization.

Papers:

“Discursive Opportunities and the Motivational Framing of Human-rights Activism for East Timor,” Julian Torelli, McMaster University

“Caste and Lawfare: Anti-caste Legislations, Hinduphobia and the Case of Global Hindutva in the US,” Debadatta Chakraborty, University of Massachusetts Amherst

“Macro-micro Interaction in Knowledge Construction: Structural and Communicative Memory in Rwanda and Sierra Leone,” Jillian P. LaBranche, University of Minnesota

“Community and Belonging: The Role of Collective Narratives and Meta-stories in the Decision-making of Iranians in the Atlantic Canadian Cities,” Foroogh Mohammadi, Acadia University

4:30pm – 5:30pm Plenary Session

PLENARY

Session 078: Presidential Address
Room: Ballroom Centre

Sponsor: Program Committee

Introduction: Elizabeth A. Armstrong, University of Michigan

President: Mary Bernstein, University of Connecticut

Presidential Address:

Another Damn Day in America: Racism and the Politics of Gun Violence Prevention

5:45pm – 7:00pm Plenary Session

PLENARY

Session 079: Awards Ceremony
Room: Ballroom Centre

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizer &

President: Mary Bernstein, University of Connecticut

AWARDS TO BE PRESENTED

- SSSP Division Awards: Winners of the Student Paper Competitions
- Arlene Kaplan Daniels Paper Award
- Beth B. Hess Memorial Scholarship
- C. Wright Mills Award
- Doris Wilkinson Faculty Leadership Award
- The Ewing Marion Kauffman Foundation: Awards in Social Entrepreneurship and Innovation
- Indigenous Peoples' Social Justice Award
- Joseph B. Gittler Award
- Kathleen S. Lowney Mentoring Award
- Lee Founders Award
- Racial/Ethnic Minority Graduate Fellowship
- Thomas C. Hood Social Action Award

7:15pm – 8:15pm Reception

Division-Sponsored Reception: Open to SSSP Registrants

Location: Ballroom Foyer

All meeting registrants are invited to the Division-Sponsored Reception. This social hour provides opportunities to renew past acquaintances, chat with old friends, and find a newcomer to befriend. New members and first-time meeting attendees are particularly encouraged to attend. Complimentary beer, wine, and non-alcoholic beverages and heavy hors d'oeuvres will be available.

Sunday, August 11

8:00am – 12:00pm Meeting

Board of Directors, 2024-25

Room: Salon 1

8:30am – 10:10am Sessions

THEMATIC

Session 080: Gender-Based Violence: Women and Victimization

Room: Drummond West

Sponsors: Crime and Justice
Family
Gender
Sexual Behavior, Politics, and Communities

Organizer &

Presider: Lloyd Klein, LaGuardia Community College

Description:

This session highlights gender-based violence as represented by presentations focused on women's lives, offender demographics, community reentry, and sexual assault.

Papers:

“U.S. Female Sex Offender Demographics, 2010-2022,” Amelia Roskin-Fraze, University of California, Irvine

“Violence against Women and Reentry,” Cynthia Baiqing Zhang, Evergreen Campus LLC

“Sexual Assault Victims and Forensic Interventions in Rural Scotland and Ontario: Compounded Inequities and Continued Injustices,” Deborah White, Trent University, Andrea Quinlan, University of Waterloo, Lesley McMillan, Glasgow Caledonian University, Gethin Rees, Newcastle University, Lou Clave, Glasgow Caledonian University, Jenniffer Olenewa and Jessica Gill, University of Waterloo

“Stochastic Gender-based Violence: How Incels Justify and Encourage Sexualized Violence against Women,” Michael Halpin, Meghan Gosse and Finlay Maguire, Dalhousie University

“In the Belly of the Beast: Impact of Gender-based Violence on the Lives of Woman,” Lloyd Klein, LaGuardia Community College

Session 081: Shared Identity Making and Mental Illness

Room: Drummond Centre

Sponsors: Disability
Society and Mental Health

Organizers: Melinda Leigh Maconi, Moffitt Cancer Center
Douglas J. Engelman, University of North Carolina
Wilmington

Presider &

Discussant: Melinda Leigh Maconi, Moffitt Cancer Center

Description:

Impact of Social Media Websites Targeting Individuals with Eating Disorders

Papers:

“Childhood Trauma and the Impact on Mental Health Later in Life,” Marissa Button, University of North Carolina Wilmington, Honorable Mention in the Society and Mental Health Division’s Student Paper Competition

“Impact of Social Media Websites Targeting Individuals with Eating Disorders,” Savannah Moriarty, University of North Carolina Wilmington

“Overlooked: Hoarding as Trauma-tainment,” Liz Wilcox, Boston College

SPECIAL

Session 082: GIFTS: Good Ideas for Teaching Sociology and Publishing in TRAILS

Room: Drummond East

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Jacqueline M. Zalewski, West Chester University of Pennsylvania

Description:

In this workshop, participants identify their great ideas for teaching sociology and learn how to use TRAILS. Participants will be able to get any questions they might have about TRAILS answered, learn insider tips for TRAILS users and individuals who want to submit, learn about the qualities of a good submission, and leave with a good idea for teaching by way of demonstrating a published activity.

THEMATIC

Session 083: Necropolitics: The Death Worlds of Drug Wars

Room: Hemon

Sponsor: Program Committee

Organizer &

Presider: Dolores Trevizo, Occidental College

Discussant: R.A. Dello Buono, Manhattan College

Description:

Whether because of the role of states or of nonstate armed actors, the contemporary world is afflicted by what Achille

Mbembé calls “*death worlds*,” “new and unique forms of social existence in which vast populations are subjected to conditions of life conferring upon them the status of the *living dead*.” The papers on this panel will discuss the death worlds associated with the war on drugs in Mexico, the Philippines, Central America and the United States.

Papers:

“The Collateral Damage of Mexico’s Drug War,” Dolores Trevizo, Occidental College

“Rodrigo Duterte’s War on Drugs in the Philippines,” Ligaya Lindio McGovern, Emeritus Professor of Sociology, Indiana University Kokomo

“The Role of the Drug Trade in Refugee Flows from Central America,” Leisy J. Abrego, University of California, Los Angeles

“Death by Politics: Three Counties in the U.S. and Their Approach to the Opioid Crisis,” Gabreélla Friday, Watson Institute for International and Public Affairs and Center for the Study of Race and Ethnicity, Brown University and Nilüfer Akalin, Lyman Briggs College at Michigan State University

Session 084: Violating Norms: Unlawful Bodies in Public Spaces

Room: Jarry

Sponsors: Law and Society
Sport, Leisure, and the Body

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Jinsun Yang, University of Oregon

Description:

This session delves into the social construct of “unlawful bodies” in public spaces. By examining the politics of spatiality, legitimacy, and the hierarchy of the body, the session will explore the meanings and locations of “unlawful bodies” at the intersection of sex, race, class, ability, age, religion, appearance, citizenship status, nationality, and more.

Papers:

“‘Even When I Wasn’t Large, I Felt Large’: Fatphobia and Women Baby Boomers,” Jeannine A. Galey, Texas Christian University

“Be Nice Until It’s Time to Not Be Nice: Bouncers as Experience Makers and Place Makers at a College Bar,” Michael O. Johnston, William Penn University

“Body Modification Practices and Sexual Identities,” David C. Lane, Illinois State University, Gifty Asiamah, Temple University and Whitney DeCamp, Western Michigan University

“Justice for Juveniles in Morocco,” Taylor Lee, School for International Training and Salve Regina University

Session 085: Migration, Mobility, and Place in Global Context

Room: Joyce

Sponsors: Global
Poverty, Class, and Inequality

Organizer: Judith R. Halasz, SUNY New Paltz

Presider &

Discussant: Frank Ridzi, Le Moyne College and Central New York Community Foundation

Description:

This session explores social processes of changing place, from immigration to housing relocation. How do people navigate the challenges associated with finding their place as they move through the world? How do migration and mobility transform place-based identities, opportunities, and resources in a globalized world? And how do race, class, gender, nationality, and the environment inform experiences of migration and mobility?

Papers:

“Immigration Narratives of Loss and Belonging,” Amir B. Marvasti and Travis B. Saylor, Penn State Altoona

“Does Race Matter in the Race to Citizenship? An Asian Indian Immigrant Perspective,” Reema Sen, Case Western Reserve University

“Housing Aspirations in Turbulent Times: The Struggles and Strategies of Highly-educated Young People amidst Housing Crisis,” Tangi Pui-chi Yip, Gender Research Center of The Chinese University of Hong Kong

“Are High Lead Poisoning Rates Associated with Family Relocation to Safer Neighborhoods? Implications for Public Policy,” Frank Ridzi, Le Moyne College and Central New York Community Foundation and Colby Cyrus, Central New York Community Foundation

THEMATIC

Session 086: Institutional Inequalities and Violence

Room: Kafka

Sponsor: Critical Race and Ethnic Study

Organizer &

Presider: Watoii Rabii, Oakland University

Description:

This session involves multiple manifestations and intersections of violence in institutions.

Papers:

“‘Rinse and Repeat, The Same Old Thing’: How My Yogic Informed Autoethnographic Research Allowed Me to ‘Survive the Stop’ and Prevented Me from Being Shot (Possibly Murdered) by Law Enforcement at a Gas Station in Holton, Kansas. While Allowing Me to Heal and Discuss the Trauma Safely as a Black Man,” Brett Lesley Cumberbatch, University of Manitoba

“Dignified Partnership in Black and White: A Critical Analysis on the Clash between Black Feminist Thought and White Saviorism,” Chidimma Ozor Commer, University of Michigan

“Harmonies of Contention: Unveiling the Hidden Narratives of Country Music through Content Analysis,” Olivia Yoh, University of Miami

“How Much Change is Change Enough? Examining Gender Transition in the Context Discretionary Parole Release,” Kimberly D. Richman, University of San Francisco, Valerie Jenness, University of California, Irvine and Claire Simonich, Unaffiliated

“They Haven’t Been Sued Yet: Hooked by Capitalism and Caught in Legal Netting,” Jordan C. Grasso, University of California, Irvine

Session 087: Ethnography/Institutional Ethnography and the Environment

Room: Lamartine

Sponsors: Environment and Technology
Institutional Ethnography

Organizers: Lauren Eastwood, SUNY, Plattsburgh
Haisu Huang, University of Oregon

Presider: Lauren Eastwood, SUNY, Plattsburgh

Description:

This session presents critical work from India, Canada, and the US, using ethnographic methods to understand societal and environmental interactions. Issues in this session cover community organizing, institutional violence in healthcare, climate disasters, in both rural and urban setting, on both the institutional and individual levels.

Papers:

“‘Re-emergence of the Commons’: How Central Pennsylvania Communities Find Support and a Voice through Community Gardening,” Andrew Thomas Silliker, The Pennsylvania State University

“Connecting the Social with the Environmental: Bringing Institutional Ethnography into Conversation with Urban Political Ecology,” Mitchell McLarnon, Concordia University

“How Place Matters in Disaster Survivors’ Journey Back Home: An Ethnographic Study of the 2020 Holiday Farm Fire,” Haisu Huang, University of Oregon

“Interrogating Power and Politics in Community Development Partnerships: The Case of a Grassroots Community Based Organization in Rural Rajasthan, India,” Prerna Rana, University of Wisconsin Madison

“Violent Space: An Institutional Ethnography on Emergency Nurse Work in a Radically Redesigned Department,” Sophie Pomerleau, CISSS de la Montérégie-Est

Session 088: PAR and Organizing in Social Movement Spaces
Room: Musset

Sponsors: Community Research and Development
Conflict, Social Action, and Change

Organizers & Presiders: C. Michael Awsumb, Northwest Missouri State University
Thomas Pineros-Shields, University of Massachusetts Lowell

Description:

Papers in this session present findings from and discuss experiences doing community-based, participatory action, and ethnographic research on community organizing, civic engagement, and social movement activism.

Papers:

“‘Making the New One to Push out the Old One’: Conflicts as Property for a Mutual Aid Collective,” Zachary J. Kyle, University of Illinois at Chicago

“Joining the Mutual Aid Community Movement: Participatory Action Research as Praxis in the Mutual Aid Community Movement,” C. Michael Awsumb, Northwest Missouri State University and Michael Lee Hurst Jr., Swansea Mutual Aid Resource Treasury

“The Mirage of Democracy: How the Political Process Erodes Political Trust and Nurtures Critical Citizens,” Sadie Dempsey, University of Wisconsin

“Collaborative Reflections on a Joint ‘Lab’ Configuration in CBPR,” Molly Clark-Barol, University of Wisconsin-Madison

“Centering Voices and Stories of Immigrant and Refugee Youth through Co-designing and Documenting a Community Garden,” Riann Lognon, Santanu Dutta, Megha Sanyal, Pallavi Banerjee, Pratim Sengupta and Newcomer Youth Research Team, University of Calgary

10:30am – 12:10pm Sessions

Session 089: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: The Changing Impact of Technologies on Mental Health
Room: Salon 5

Sponsors: Health, Health Policy, and Health Services Society and Mental Health

Organizers: Yuying Shen, Norfolk State University
Douglas J. Engelman, University of North Carolina Wilmington

Presider/

Discussant: Yuying Shen, Norfolk State University

Description:

An in-depth discussion on the impact of changing technologies on our mental health.

Papers:

“‘Better Safe Than Sorry’: Prepping, COVID-19, and the Influence of Masculine Norms. Is This Something New?” Andrew Thomas Silliker, The Pennsylvania State University

“Digital Disparity and Mental Health Equity: The Mental Health Impacts of Cyberbullying among Adolescents,” Yuying Shen, Norfolk State University

“Doom Scrolling: How Does Constant Exposure to Violent and Traumatic Media Impact Our Worldview and Mental Health?” Spencer Boatwright, University of North Carolina Wilmington

“Exploring Dating App Usage and Addiction,” Laura S. Hatvany, University of North Carolina Wilmington

THEMATIC

Session 090: Criminalizing Immigration
Room: Drummond West

Sponsors: Crime and Justice
Family
Global
Law and Society
Poverty, Class, and Inequality

Organizer: Rafia Javaid Mallick, Georgia State University

Presider &

Discussant: Melissa Maxey, University of Oklahoma

Description:

This conference session promises a deep dive into the intricate layers of the United States immigration system, shedding light on its profound impact on various marginalized communities. Our esteemed panel of researchers will present four compelling

papers that encourage critical dialogue and foster a better understanding of the multifaceted issues surrounding race, surveillance, homonationalism, and crimmigration. Don’t miss this opportunity to engage with cutting-edge research and contribute to the ongoing discourse on immigration policy and its consequences.

Papers:

“Crimmigration and Critical Criminology: Policing the Relative Surplus Population,” David B. Feldman, Oberlin College

“From Criminalization to Deportation: Race in the United States Immigration System,” Sarah Tosh, Rutgers University-Camden

“Quotidian Homonationalism: Green Card Adjudication, Immigration Law, and Liberal Inclusion of Same-sex Binational Marriages,” Juhwan Seo, Cornell University, Winner of the Family Division’s Student Paper Competition

“Unbounded Surveillance: Punishing Visitors in and out of U.S. Immigration Detention,” Luis A. Romero, Texas Christian University

Session 091: Activism for Social Change
CANCELLED

Session 092: Organizing in the Workplace
Room: Drummond East

Sponsor: Labor Studies

Organizer &

Presider: Emily Helen An-Mei Yen, University of Virginia

Description:

This panel explores the praxis of fighting for better working conditions through collective action. Workers in the United States and Canada have increasingly decided to unionize when facing harsh working conditions. Members of several labor unions will examine the challenges they faced organizing their workplace, building a campaign, and preparing for a strike. Panelists will also reflect on the lessons they learned, and they could be applied to other workers facing similar challenges.

Panelists:

Kelsey Weymouth-Little, University of California, Irvine

Shannon Ikebe, John Abbott College

Edwin Everhart, Pittsburgh Federation of Teachers 400

Session 093: Problematizing the Medicalization of Addiction

Room: Hemon

Sponsors: Drinking and Drugs
Social Problems Theory

Organizer & President: Joshua H. Stout, Illinois State University

Discussant: Benjamin Fleury-Steiner, University of Delaware

Description:

This session explores the medicalization of addiction by examining the consequences of this framework on individuals and institutions.

Papers:

"Analyzing and Replacing the Moral-disease Model of Addiction," Andrew R. Burns, Louisiana State University

"Challenging Biomedical Constructions of Risk among People Who Use Drugs," David Frank, Luther Elliott, Charles M. Cleland and Alexander S. Bennett, New York University

"Recovery Denied: Bereaved Survivors' Stories of Institutional Stigma and the Necrotherapeutic State in Drug Treatment," Joshua H. Stout, Illinois State University, Benjamin Fleury-Steiner and Tim Chesnik, University of Delaware

"What are the Consequences of Medicalization? An Autoethnographic Account of Losing My Mom to Opioid Addiction," Hope E. Ousey, Wilkes University

THEMATIC

Session 094: Trauma and the Life Course

Room: Jarry

Sponsor: Youth, Aging, and the Life Course

Organizer & President: Brittney Miles, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign

Description:

This panel explores various ways trauma-informed research shapes our understanding of phenomena across the life course. Specifically, the papers in this panel will examine trauma related to victimization, childhood sexual experiences and PTSD, intimate partner violence, military veteran's exposure to violence, and older women's experiences of homelessness. These papers interrogate the relationship between trauma and the life course to consider its impact among diverse populations and across diverse social issues.

Papers:

"Adolescent Violence, Victimization, and Later Civic Engagement: The Role of Agency," Andrew Wilczak and Emily E. Roberts, Wilkes University

"An Experiential Intimate Partner Violence Recidivism Intervention: A Trauma-Informed Transformative Justice Approach with Racialized Allophone Immigrants," Katherine Maurer, McGill University

"Appraisals of Childhood Sexual Experiences, PTSD, and Help-seeking Behavior among Black and Latino Sexual Minority Men," Martin J. Downing, Lehman College, CUNY, Ellen Benoit, North Jersey Community Research Initiative and Jason M. Dotson, Wellness with Jason Dotson, LLC

"Exposure to Violence and Mental Health: Explanations from Life Course Perspective, Cumulative Adversity Theory, and the Stress Process Model on Military Veteran Mental Health," Amanda C. McGowan, Baylor University

"The Importance of Life Course and Intersectionality Perspectives for Understanding Older Women's Homelessness: Social Identity, Social Othering, and Marginalization," Judith G. Gonyea, Boston University and Keily Melekis, University of Vermont

Session 095: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Identity Matters: How an Instructor's Subjectivity Influences the Way They Teach about Race

Room: Joyce

Sponsors: Critical Race and Ethnic Study
Teaching Social Problems

Organizer & President/

Discussant: Florence Emily Castillo, The University of Texas at Dallas

Description:

This session explores how the subjectivity of instructors impacts our theoretical interpretations of race and shapes the pedagogical choices we make when we teach race in the classroom. Intersectional and critical race scholars continue to call our attention to how lived experiences also influence the ways we process and disseminate information both in and outside the classroom. With this in mind, we seek to further explore how our intersectional identities create the embodied pedagogies and experiences we bring into the classroom. We hope to share classroom experiences that lead to more critical and transformative self-reflection and strategies for teaching race, especially in the current political climate where teaching about race is under attack.

Papers:

“Oral History as Embodied Classroom Pedagogy,” Jacqueline Daugherty and Rodney D. Coates, Miami University

“Feeling Teaching Race,” Adriana Leela Bohm, Delaware County Community College, Michelle Byng, Donna-Marie Peters and Mary Stricker, Temple University

“A White Woman from the South’: Social Location and the Pedagogy of Race,” Karyn McKinney Marvasti, Penn State Altoona

“Parallel Cultures: Creating Alternative Spaces of Truth-telling through Activist-based Curriculum Development and Community Outreach in the Rural Black South,” Masonya J. Bennett, Kennesaw State University

“Operationalizing Anti-oppression in Doctoral Health Care Education,” Katerina Melino, University of Alberta and Samantha P. Louie-Poon, Dalhousie University

“White Professors of Race: Ethics, Strategies, and Impacts,” Devon R. Goss, Oxford College of Emory University

THEMATIC

Session 096: Policing Environmental Problems: Who is Responsible and Who is Accountable
Room: Kafka

Sponsor: Environment and Technology

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Angus A. Nurse, Anglia Ruskin University and Nottingham Trent University

Description:

Green criminologist Rob White (2007, 2012) suggests that given the potential for environmental harms to extend far beyond the impact on individual victims that are the norm with “traditional” crimes of interpersonal violence and property crime, green crimes should be given importance if not priority within justice systems.

Yet the policing of environmental problems and crimes is often left to environmental regulators rather than mainstream policing agencies which risks environmental “crimes” being classified as somehow less important than mainstream crimes. This panel considers the question of how environmental problems should be “policed” and who should be responsible for doing so. This includes examining different policies; perspectives and enforcement approaches and some case studies relating to specific environmental problems.

Papers:

“Conservatism, the Far Right, and the Environment,” Jesse C. Bryant and Justin Farrell, Yale University

“Corporations, Carbon, and Climate: Examining the Macrosociological Determinants of Corporate Emissions,” Annika Rieger, Singapore Management University

“Environmental Justice as Transformative Justice; Transformative Justice as Environmental Justice,” Jeff Feng, Northwestern University and Melanie Brazzell, Harvard University

“Mediating the Human Impacts of Environmental Harms: The Case for an Ecojustice Approach,” Angus A. Nurse, Anglia Ruskin University and Nottingham Trent University

THEMATIC

Session 097: Theorized versus Everyday Experiences of Violence
Room: Lamartine

Sponsors: Conflict, Social Action, and Change Institutional Ethnography

Organizers: Naomi E. Nichols, Trent University
C. Michael Awsumb, Northwest Missouri State University

Presider: Naomi E. Nichols, Trent University

Description:

Papers in this session explore how institutional ethnography can be used to investigate violence (institutional, state, inter-personal) as it is experienced, rather than as it is theorized.

Papers:

“‘But You’re American’ - Positionality and Reflexivity among Black Researchers Examining Antiracism in Central/Eastern Europe,” Bryan L. Greene, University of Connecticut

“Anchoring Investigations of Institutional Violence in Experience – Examples from Institutional Ethnography,” Naomi E. Nichols, Trent University

“Identities of Violence, Identities of Healing: Residential School Survivors Represent Themselves,” Lily Ivanova, University of British Columbia

“Theory and Practice in Peer Support and Community-led Advocacy: Theorizing as a Tool for Making Sense of Everyday Spaces of Violence,” Jayne Malenfant, McGill University

“Violence, Resistance, Ethnography, and Critical Criminology: Working towards an Institutional Ethnography Agenda in Victimology and Crimes of the Powerful,” C. Michael Awsumb, Northwest Missouri State University

Session 098: Accessible Cities

Room: Musset

Sponsors: Community Research and Development
Sport, Leisure, and the Body

Organizer &

President: Michael O. Johnston, William Penn University

Description:

The sociological study of cities and urban life is one of the field's oldest sub-disciplines. Urban sociologists' study and examine the social, historical, political, cultural, economic, and environmental forces that have shaped urban environments. This field of study focuses on things like poverty, racial residential segregation, economic development, migration and demographic trends, gentrification, homelessness, blight and crime, urban decline, and neighborhood changes and revitalization. Such critical insights provided by the analyses conducted by urban sociologists can be used to shape and guide urban planning and policymaking.

This regular session brings scholars together to talk about their research on the accessibility (and inaccessibility) of cities.

Papers:

"A Proposed Phenomenological Investigation of Exclusion to Blue and Green Spaces in Rural Cities," Peder E. Schillemat, University of West Georgia

"Black Mecca, U.S.A: An in-depth Look at Race, Class, and Placemaking in Atlanta, Georgia," Jonathan P. Grant, University of North Florida

"Reimagining Public Parks: Latinx Identity and Community Perceptions of Safety," Ileri Bernal, University of Massachusetts Lowell, Lillian Wynne Platten and Teresa Irene Gonzales, Loyola University Chicago

"The Journey towards Inclusive Tourism: Assessing Accessibility in Kathmandu, Nepal," Ramesh Khanal, Saraswati Multiple Campus

"Urban Labs beyond Europe: The Formation of Experimental Community Climate Governance in Five Latin American Cities," Michael Roll, University of Wisconsin-Madison and German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS), Florencia Almansi, International Institute for Environment and Development-América Latina, Jorgelina Hardoy, International Institute for Environment and Development, Simone Gatti, World Resources Institute, Brazil, Ariadne Samios, World Resources Institute, Lucas Turmena, United Nations University and Institute for Environment and Human Security, Mariana Campos, World Resources Institute and Gorka Zubizaray, World Resources Institute, Mexico

12:00pm – 1:30pm

Special Session at ASA

SPECIAL

Session 116: Life in Sociology Lecture: Born a Sociologist by Dr. Barbara Katz Rothman
Room: Palais des Congrès de Montréal, Level 5, Room 515C

Sponsors: American Sociological Association Retirement Network
Program Committee

Organizer: Judith A. Howard, University of Washington

President: Mary Lou Finley, Antioch University Seattle

Description:

The Life in Sociology Lecture is co-sponsored with the American Sociological Association.

Barbara Katz Rothman, PhD, is Professor of Sociology, Public Health, Disability Studies and Women's Studies at the City University of New York. She has her BA and MA from Brooklyn College, PhD from NYU. She is the author of several books, including, most recently, *The Biomedical Empire: Lessons Learned from the Covid-19 Pandemic*. She is Past President of Sociologists for Women in Society; the Society for the Study of Social Problems, and the Eastern Sociological Society. She was the Fulbright-Saastamoinen Foundation Distinguished Chair in Health Sciences 2018-2019 and is a proud recipient of an award for "Midwifing the Movement" from the Midwives Alliance of North America.

Panelist:

Barbara Katz Rothman, The Graduate Center, CUNY

12:30pm – 2:10pm

Sessions

THEMATIC

Session 099: Intersections of Health, Criminal Justice, and Harm Reduction
Room: Drummond West

Sponsors: Crime and Justice
Sociology and Social Welfare

Organizer &

President: Cynthia Baiqing Zhang, Evergreen Campus LLC

Description:

This session is focused on how health, criminal justice, and harm reduction are inter-related. The contact with the criminal justice system is significant for people's lives, including health. The criminal justice system is supposed to reduce harm. That is, the criminal justice system is assigned the tasks of social security explicitly and social wellbeing implicitly. In this session, we

explore the inter-connection of health, criminal justice, and harm reduction with theoretical and empirical studies. Because vulnerable people (e.g. women, minority, low-income individuals, LGBTQ community, and others) are overrepresented in the inmate population in the U.S., this session is also informed by scholarship on inequality.

Papers:

“Disrupting Constructions: How Prison Dog Rehabilitation Programs Destabilize Racialized Arrangements during and after Incarceration,” Jennifer K. Wesely, University of North Florida and Gennifer Furst, William Paterson University

“Exploring the Impact of a Cathartic Movement Program (Dance to be Free) on Incarcerated Women,” Timbre L. Wulf, Central State University, Suzanne L. Maughan Spencer and Julie N. Campbell, University of Nebraska Kearney

“Harm Reduction and Reproductive Health for Peripregnant Women Who Use Drugs and Have a History of Incarceration in the U.S.,” Kathryn Nowotny and Melanie McKenna, University of Miami, Krystle Culbertson and Danielle Estes, LEAP for Ladies, Jessica Younts, Florida Justice Center & Justice Impact Alliance, Katrina Ciraldo and Teresa Chueng, University of Miami and Edward Suarez, University of Miami Miller School of Medicine

“Methadone Access in Police Custody Healthcare as Denied Care: Professional Risk Discourses and the Patient Group Directive,” Gethin Rees, Newcastle University

“Trauma, Gender, and The Criminal(izing) Justice System: A Critical Review of Sentencing,” Josephine A. Barnett, The Graduate Center, CUNY

Session 100: Teaching Social Problems in Time of Polarization

Room: Drummond Centre

Sponsor: Teaching Social Problems

Organizers: Perri S. Levis, Rhode Island College
Katie Founds, Independent Scholar
Jennifer Roebuck Bulanda, Miami University
Morena Tartari, Babes-Bolyai University

Presider: Pedrom Nasiri, University of Calgary

Description:

This session presents examples of different pedagogies and models that teachers are using to provide deep learning for both K-12 and college students in today's polarized and contentious educational environment. From the passage of legislation banning books to limiting the topics that are allowed to be discussed in the classroom, teachers today face significant challenges both in how and what they can teach. This session provides important learnings that attendees can apply to their own classroom environments.

Papers:

“Using the Social Order-social Justice Framework to Enhance Constructive Dialogue,” Monnica Gavin, Clark State College

“Empowering Critical Engagement: Teaching Sociology through Critical Pedagogy in a Polarized Era,” Carla Devonn Brailey, Texas Southern University

“Racism Evasiveness and Racism Consciousness in the Curriculum: How We Talk and Teach about Racism and Why It Matters,” Wade P. Smith, Eastern Illinois University

“Crip Pedagogies as Anti-violent, Anti-carceral Practices in the College Classroom,” Siobhan Marie Pokorney, The Graduate Center, CUNY

“‘Controversial’ Content in K-12 Schools: The Intersection of Federal and State Policy and Its Bearing on Local Implementation,” Jane Rochmes and Linda M. Waldron, Christopher Newport University, Kate Bowman, University of Delaware, Carlie Carter, College of William and Mary and Jessica Spencer, Christopher Newport University

Session 101: Reproductive Justice

Room: Hemon

Sponsors: Gender
Health, Health Policy, and Health Services
Sexual Behavior, Politics, and Communities

Organizer & Presider: Giovanna Follo, Wright State University-Lake Campus

Description:

In a time where reproductive rights are being contested, we need to advocate for reproductive justice.

Papers:

“‘Have Two Babies and Call Me in the Morning’: The Past and Current Practice of Prescribing Pregnancy to People with Endometriosis,” Colleen Kavanagh, Case Western Reserve University

“‘I Left There Just Like Crying’: Black Doulas’ Response to Gender and Race-based Violence in Correctional Institutions,” Denae Bradley-Morris, Howard University

“Counter-narratives about Breastfeeding in Black Newspapers,” Shannon K. Carter, University of Central Florida and Bhoomi K. Thakore, University of Connecticut

“Seahorses on Social Media: Analyzing #SeahorseDads and Pregnant Trans* Men on TikTok,” Athanasia Angela Platis, Georgia State University

“The Experiences and Priorities of Women with Disabilities Regarding Reproduction and Pregnancy in Alberta, Canada,” Eleni Moumos, Alan Santinele Martino and Erin Brennand, University of Calgary

Session 102: Institutional Ethnographies of Law, Crime, and Justice

Room: Jarry

Sponsors: Institutional Ethnography
Law and Society

Organizers: Catherine Hastings, Macquarie University
Colin Hastings, University of Waterloo

Presider & Discussant: Colin Hastings, University of Waterloo

Description:

This session brings together critical scholars who examine the social organization of legal systems and the everyday work of those caught up inside of these systems. While the empirical sites that these projects examine are vast, they share a common commitment to bringing into view the social relations that shape law, crime, and justice. In making the systemic violence of legal systems visible, these projects enhance understandings of how to mobilize resistance and meaningful change.

Papers:

“Besieging International Law: The Case of Palestine and CEDAW,” Zaina Jallad Charpentier, Harvard Law School

“Legitimizing Strategies: Pretrial Risk Assessments and the Logics of Data-driven Judicial Discretion,” Sino V. Esthappan, Northwestern University, Winner of the Law and Society Division’s Student Paper Competition

“Mortality Tracking as Data Justice: An Ethnography into a Community-based Data Infrastructure Seeking to Address Homelessness,” Maxime Goulet-Langlois, McGill University

“The Social Construction of Justice and Rehabilitation in Family Court,” Mary Elizabeth Underwood Hood, University of Nevada, Las Vegas

THEMATIC

Session 103: Violence and Theory

Room: Joyce

Sponsor: Social Problems Theory

Organizer & Presider: Joshua H. Stout, Illinois State University

Description:

This session broadly explores theoretical contributions to our understanding of violence, the impacts and implications of violence, and cultures of violence.

Papers:

“Habituating the Police,” Justin Turner, Illinois State University and Travis Milburn, Penn State Shenango

“Imagining Social Collapse: Intersectional Representation in Apocalyptic Cultural Field,” Jonathan Nathaniel Redman, University of California, Irvine

“Peculiar Sensations: Toward A (Racialized) Sociology of Violence,” Endia Hayes, Dartmouth College

“Violence by Design: How Mobile and Spatialized Violence Shape Urban Spaces,” Gwendolyn Purifoye, University of Notre Dame

“‘Peace is Dangerous’: Du Bois’ Theory of Colonial Post-fascism,” Ali Meghji, University of Cambridge

Session 104: The Costs of Higher Ed

Room: Kafka

Sponsor: Educational Problems

Organizer, Presider & Discussant: Myron T. Strong, Community College of Baltimore County

Description:

The papers in this section focus on the emotional, physical, academic and other labor individuals experience caused by the higher education and grant funding institutions. While there is a sort of freedom that comes with education, there is a cost navigating the structure.

Papers:

“‘Ungrading’ through the Back Door: Academic Assessment Instead of Grades?” Jacob Heller, SUNY Old Westbury

“A Moral Dilemma of ‘Selling Out’: Race, Class, and Career Considerations among Elite College Students,” Joyce Kim, University of Pennsylvania, Winner of the Educational Problems Division’s Student Paper Competition

“Intersectional Microaggressions in Transnational Contexts: Black Students Experiencing Gendered, Ableist, and Queer-phobic Anti-blackness in the U.S. and South Africa,” Assata Zerai, University of New Mexico

“The Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on International Students’ Future Career and Migration Plans,” Eugena Kwon, Trent University

Session 105: Patterns and Practices of Resistance, Solidarity, and Organizing vis-à-vis the Conditions of Poverty and Inequality

Room: Lamartine

Sponsors: Conflict, Social Action, and Change
Poverty, Class, and Inequality

Organizer: Sara Maani, University of Milan-Bicocca

Presider & Discussant: TBD

Description:

This session aims at delving into the intricate dynamics of resistance, solidarity, and organizing emerging in response to the pressing issues of poverty, class, and inequality. We invite papers with the empirical research and theoretical discussions that explore varied patterns and practices that marginalized communities employ to confront and navigate multiple conditions of inequality through acts of resistance and solidarity for collective empowerment and social change. This session aims to foster a deeper understanding of the ways in which grassroots movements and community organizations challenge existing power structures and advocate for equitable solutions. We invite attendees to critically reflect on the complexities of social organizing and the potential for transformative action in the face of adversity and inequality.

Papers:

“‘I’m Pretty Bad at This, Dude’: Attending to Social Class and Power in Qualitative Research,” Shelley M. Kimelberg, SUNY University at Buffalo

“‘It’s the Stupid Food System Here’: Emotions, Solidarity, and Community Building in Food Access Spaces,” Julie Schweitzer and Tamara L. Mix, Oklahoma State University

“On Building a Criminology of Revolutions,” Andrew Wilczak, Wilkes University

Session 106: Crisis and Globalization(s)

Room: Musset

Sponsor: Global

Organizer & Presider: David A. Smith, University of California, Irvine

Description:

The papers in this session cover a lot of topics in the area of world-system analysis. Come hear from junior scholars and faculty members alike as they present on issues of food, water, the Global South, tech workers, and issues of inequality and

hierarchy. All five papers will dive deep on some very interesting topics!

Papers:

“A taste for terroir: The science and politics of the EU’s global geographical indication development agenda,” Matthew J. Zinsli, University of Wisconsin–Madison

“Comparative Analysis of Public Response to Mexico’s Junk Food Labeling Policy,” A. Susana Ramirez, University of California, Merced

“Privilege is a Prison: Indian Tech Workers Facing Covert Carcerality in India and the US,” Rianka Roy, University of Connecticut

“Why’s the Water Gone?: The Treadmill of Production through Global Water Exploitation,” Joshua C. Cafferty, Utah Tech University

“World-system Hierarchy, Economic Productivity, and Global Economic Downturns: Analyzing Trade Networks Post-2008 Global Financial Crisis,” Martin Jacinto, California State University, Chico

2:30pm – 4:10pm Meeting

Council of Division Chairpersons and Program Chair, 2024-25

Room: Salon 1

2:30pm – 4:10pm Sessions

Session 107: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Critical Race and Rural Studies

Room: Salon 5

Sponsors: Community Research and Development
Social Problems Theory

Organizer & Presider/

Discussant: Nathaniel Dumas, Xoogle Founders-Researchers Hub

Description:

Critical Rural Theory transformed sociologies of rurality by encouraging the study of rurality through conceptual lenses of structure, space, and culture. While they note similarities between spatial and racial identities, these scholars have yet to explore how political economies of race create competing experiences of rurality. Similarly, Critical Race Theorists pushed disciplines to problematize and move beyond simplistic comparisons and demographic understandings of race. While some of their work decenters “place-centricism,” these scholars have yet to make use of transformative conversations happening within Critical Rural Theory.

Through dialogue, we aim for Critical Rural Theorists to cultivate complex perspectives of how race complicates rurality and for

Critical Race Theorists to incorporate complex rethinking of rurality that further problematize studying racial articulations.

Papers:

“Intersections of Race and Rurality: Settlement Space as Medium of Oppression,” Alexander R. Thomas and Gregory M. Fulkerson, SUNY Oneonta, Karen Hayden, Merrimack College and Polly J. Smith, Utica University

“Critical Race Theory: Identity, Place, and Exclusion,” Kalwant Bhopal, University of Birmingham and Martin Myers, University of Nottingham

“The Very Very Far North: Considering Canada’s Northern Tier through the Lenses of Critical Rural Theory and Critical Race Theory,” Aimee Vieira, CanNor

“Rural Land Tenure and the Racial Wealth Gap,” Natasha Moodie and Keith Wiley, Housing Assistance Council

“Indigenous Identity and Struggles for State Recognition in Ecuador,” Caroline Martinez, University of California, Irvine

THEMATIC

Session 108: The Social Construction of Violence

Room: Drummond West

Sponsor: Crime and Justice

Organizer: Kylie Parrotta, California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo

Presider &

Discussant: Karmvir Kaur Padda, University of Waterloo

Description:

The session will focus on narrative criminology, specifically how people use narratives to explain violent behavior that may or may not be seen as criminal. Papers will focus on violent offenders, immigrant experiences, and practitioners’ assessments of programs and court processes.

Papers:

“(De)Racializing Victimhood: Narratives of Service Workers at the Human Trafficking Intervention Courts,” Yen-Chiao Liao, Siena College

“Constructing Effectiveness: Men’s Anti-violence Program Practitioners’ Narratives of Success,” Doug Schrock and Hailey S. McGee, Florida State University

“Narratives of Radicalization: The Role of Manifestos in Shaping Extremist Violence,” Karmvir Kaur Padda, University of Waterloo

“The Brutalization of Immigrants in the Line at the Questura in Italy,” Robert Garot, John Jay College of Criminal Justice, CUNY

THEMATIC

Session 109: Systemic Vulnerabilities and Technology

Room: Drummond Centre

Sponsor: Environment and Technology

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Nels Paulson, University of Wisconsin-Stout

Description:

The 21st century is largely defined by forces of globalization and digital technologies. Shifts for society in these ways must be understood in all their complexities. This session explores the ways in which technology amplifies or resists inequities in society.

Papers:

“Automating the Automators: De/Up-skilling and Re/Off-shoring in Globalized Software Work,” Bhumika Chauhan, New York University, Winner of the Labor Studies Division’s Student Paper Competition

“COVID-19, Teens, and ‘Silver Linings’: Exploring Some ‘Positive’ Experiences during the Pandemic,” Michael Adorjan, University of Calgary and Rosemary Ricciardelli, Memorial University of Newfoundland

“Equity and Inclusion in Hospital-at-home: How Can We Study This?” Nels Paulson and Jeffrey Sweat, University of Wisconsin-Stout

“Addressing Challenges for Rural Health Care: The Promises and Perils of Technological Solutions,” Nels Paulson, University of Wisconsin-Stout

Session 110: Author Meets Critics: *Behind Crimmigration: ICE, Law Enforcement, and Resistance in America* by Felicia Arriaga, The University of North Carolina Press, 2023

Room: Drummond East

Sponsor: Critical Race and Ethnic Study

Organizer &

Presider: Felicia Arriaga, Baruch College, CUNY

Description:

Felicia Arriaga will be in conversation about their book *Behind Crimmigration: ICE, Law Enforcement, and Resistance in America*.

Author: Felicia Arriaga, Baruch College, CUNY

Critics:

Jamella N. Gow, Bowdoin College

Michelle Christian, University of Tennessee, Knoxville

Nick Rodrigo, The Graduate Center, CUNY

THEMATIC

Session 111: The Social Organization of Medical Violence

Room: Hemon

Sponsors: Drinking and Drugs
Health, Health Policy, and Health Services
Institutional Ethnography
Sociology and Social Welfare

Organizers: Kathryn Nowotny, University of Miami
Colin Hastings, University of Waterloo

Presider: Kathryn Nowotny, University of Miami

Description:

This session examines how medical systems, knowledges, technologies, and expertise reproduce broad forms of structural inequity and violence. Papers reflect on how people's everyday experiences are caught up in these systems and call attention to openings for intervening in health systems in ways that promote equity and social justice.

Papers:

"Carceral to Transformative: Abolitionist Social Work Strategies and Principles," Craig Fortier, University of Waterloo

"Fractured Sueño Americano and State Violence: Immigration Processes, Labor and Power, and Drug and Alcohol Misuse among Recent Immigrants in Los Angeles," Alice Cepeda, Nefertari Rincon Guerra and Avelardo Valdez, University of Southern California

"Healthwork at the Office: An Explication of Medical History Making," Manda Ann Roddick, University of Victoria

"Producing a Licit Economy of Living Bodies: Symbolic Violence and Living Organ Donation," Matthew J.P. Strang, York University

"Where Does My Blood and Information Go? Early Reflections on an Institutional Ethnographic Study of Sero Surveillance from Clinic to Public Health," Colin Hastings, University of Waterloo, Amy Wah and Ryan Peck, HIV & AIDS Legal Clinic Ontario (HALCO), Alexander McClelland, Carleton University, Andrea Krusi, University of British Columbia, Maureen Owino, York University, Martin French, Concordia University, Michael Burtch, Maggie's Toronto Sex Work Action Project and Emerich Daroya, University of Toronto

THEMATIC

Session 112: Imagining, Building and Sustaining Alternative Forms of Justice

Room: Jarry

Sponsor: Law and Society

Organizer: Catherine Hastings, Macquarie University

Presider & Discussant: Paul Draus, University of Michigan-Dearborn

Description:

This session profiles a diverse international collection of emancipatory projects and perspectives that challenge existing practices and suggest alternative forms of justice. In each case, the papers imagine and advocate for progressive forms of transformative justice to confront oppression. They provide examples of how community and individual agency can be reclaimed and supported to oppose disempowerment and violence in justice and other institutional systems.

Papers:

"Art, Agency, and Decarceration: Imagining Alternatives to Social Exclusion," Paul Draus and Anna Muller, University of Michigan-Dearborn

"Exploring Alternative Modes of Justice in the Context of Sexual Violence in College Campuses in India," Sukanya Bhattacharya, University of Tennessee, Knoxville

"Speculative Knowledges as Anti-racism Practice for Children's Pain Research in Canada: Building Asian Liberatory Futures," Samantha P. Louie-Poon and Christine T. Chambers, Dalhousie University and Kathryn Birnie, University of Calgary

"Survivor Justice: An Abolitionist Perspective on Justice and the #MeToo Movement," Kasey Carmile Ragan, St. Edward's University

Session 113: Immigrant Youth and Education

Room: Kafka

Sponsor: Educational Problems

Organizer & Presider: Irina Chukhray, University of California, Davis

Description:

This session focuses broadly on higher education and immigrant youth in the United States and Canada. Our papers dive deep into immigrants' supports and constraints in accessing higher education by asking whether counselors are the best informational resources, by illuminating the ways in which immigrants navigate constraints and costs of educational achievement, by delving into the ways immigrants redefine

college-going habitus, by examining higher education access through mapping methodology that documents undocumented youths' access to higher education across the United States, and by exploring immigrants' experiences within STEM and higher education. The papers in this session focus on diverse immigrant groups, including African, Latinx, Asian, and other populations.

Papers:

"A Mixed-Methods Approach to Understanding Immigrant Youths' Experiences with Gathering Information about Post-Secondary Education," Irina Chukhray, University of California, Davis

"From Immigrant Legacy to Educational Future: Redefining Latinx Immigrant Familial Engagement in College-going Habitus Cultivation," Leslie Patricia Luqueno, Stanford Graduate School of Education

"Perspectives on First-generation African Immigrant Women STEM Experiences in Postsecondary Institutions in Canada," Rachael Ileh Edino, University of Calgary

"The Constraints to and Costs of Educational Achievement: Mexican Immigrant Youth in Northeast New Destinations," Jorge Ballinas, Population Research Institute, The Pennsylvania State University

"Using Mapping Methodology to Make Sense of Higher Education Access for Undocumented Students across the United States," Katherine Cumings Mansfield, University of North Texas and Paula Hernandez, University of North Carolina at Greensboro

THEMATIC

Session 114: Repertoires of Violence: Countermovement, Repression, Oppression, and Social Control
Room: Lamartine

Sponsor: Conflict, Social Action, and Change

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Marcos Perez, Washington and Lee University

Description:

In recent years, violence against dissidence and diversity has risen throughout the world. This panel will explore case studies of these phenomena and discuss potential causes, with the goal of identifying solutions.

Papers:

"Attitudes of Disposability towards MMIWG on the Highway of Tears, A CPTED Study," molly jane clare, University of Calgary

"Queer Remote Activism in the LGBTI+ Movement in Turkey," E. Ecem Ece, University of Florida

"Towards a Political Ecology of Sadism: Understanding Hindu Nationalist Cruelty as a Vehicle for Accumulation by Dispossession in India," Pratik Raghu, The New School

"Transnational Fight Clubs: The Glocalization of Fascism?" Liz Wilcox, Boston College

THEMATIC

Session 115: State and Interpersonal Violence against Contemporary Family Structures
Room: Musset

Sponsors: Family
Gender
Poverty, Class, and Inequality
Sexual Behavior, Politics, and Communities

Organizer, Presider &

Discussant: Monnica Gavin, Clark State College

Description:

Violence against and within families is an enduring social issue that has gained increasing attention in recent times. The growing awareness of how the state and individual actors are causing harm to contemporary families in societies worldwide is encouraging. In this session, we will delve into the topic of violence against families, focusing on the foster care and carceral systems, laws targeting the LGBTQIA+ community, and environmental racism.

Papers:

"State Predation? How the Carceral Care Economy Harms Black and Latine Women," Raquel Guzman Delorme, University of Southern California, Winner of the Gender Division's Student Paper Competition

"The Effect of Incarceration on the Termination of Parental Rights," Loren Beard, The University of Chicago, Winner of the Sociology and Social Welfare Division's Student Paper Competition

"Estimating the Effects of Additional Placements on Internalizing Symptoms Using Quasi-Experimental Design," Rin Ferraro, The University of Oklahoma, Honorable Mention in the Family Division's Student Paper Competition

"Environmental Injustice and Community Burden in Southern California: A Local Evaluation of the Superfund Program," Jacqueline Maria Maciel, California Lutheran University

Plenary, Thematic, and Special Sessions
(All conference programming will take place in Eastern Time.)

PLENARY SESSIONS

FRIDAY, AUGUST 9

10:30am-11:45am

Session 006: SSSP Business Meeting

11:50am-12:25pm

Session 007: Town Hall: An Open Forum

SATURDAY, AUGUST 10

4:30pm-5:30pm

Session 078: Presidential Address

5:45pm-7:00pm

Session 079: Awards Ceremony

THEMATIC SESSIONS

FRIDAY, AUGUST 9

8:30am-10:10am

Session 001: Gender-Based Violence: Institutional Issues

Session 005: Violent Environments: Empire and Colonial Legacies

12:30pm-2:10pm

Session 009: Bodies for Sale: Use of Humans and Animals for Entertainment

Session 015: Racism, Policing, and Policy Change

Session 017: Research Under Neoliberal Regimes: Peace, Human Rights, and Social Justice

2:30pm-4:10pm

Session 019: Curricular Violence: White Supremacist Silencing in Education

Session 023: Alternatives to Policing

Session 024: Institutional Ethnographies of Everyday Experiences of State Violence

Session 025: Teaching about Violence: How to Navigate Trust and Disclosure with Students

4:30pm-6:10pm

Session 030: Sex and Violence

4:30pm-6:10pm, continued

Session 033: Understanding the Sociology of Violence in a Quebecois Context/Comprendre une "sociologie de la violence" dans un contexte québécois/

Session 036: Reckoning with Institutional Violence: Perspectives across Organizational Contexts

Session 037: Culture in Conflict, Action, and Change I: Mobilization, Organizing, Resistance, and Politicization

SATURDAY, AUGUST 10

8:30am-10:10am

Session 044: Health Justice: Addressing Discrimination in Health and Health Care

Session 045: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Critical Perspectives on Law and Violence

Session 046: Unraveling the Complex Relationship between Poverty, Class, Inequality and Violence

10:30am-12:10pm

Session 048: Critical Perspectives on the Israeli-Palestinian Conflict

Session 049: Disability Embodiment: The Way Out of a System of Violence

Session 051: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Guns and Gun Violence

Session 055: Youth, Violence, and Inequality

Session 057: Feminist Abolitionism and Collective Resistance to State Control and Violence

12:30pm-2:10pm

Session 059: Criminalizing Vulnerable Populations

Session 060: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Anti-Violence and Violence: Counter-hegemony from Subversive to Revolutionary

Session 061: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Womxn's Bodies as Sites of Statist Violence: A Critique of Imperialist, Heteropatriarchal Politics

2:30pm-4:10pm

Session 069: Gender-Based Violence: Perceptions and Applications

Session 077: Culture in Conflict, Action, and Change II: Narrative, Community, Discourse, and Identity

THEMATIC SESSIONS

SUNDAY, AUGUST 11

8:30am-10:10am

- Session 080: Gender-Based Violence: Women and Victimization
- Session 083: Necropolitics: The Death Worlds of Drug Wars
- Session 086: Institutional Inequalities and Violence

10:30am-12:10pm

- Session 090: Criminalizing Immigration
- Session 094: Trauma and the Life Course
- Session 096: Policing Environmental Problems: Who is Responsible and Who is Accountable
- Session 097: Theorized versus Everyday Experiences of Violence

12:30pm-2:10pm

- Session 099: Intersections of Health, Criminal Justice, and Harm Reduction
- Session 103: Violence and Theory

2:30pm-4:10pm

- Session 108: The Social Construction of Violence
- Session 109: Systemic Vulnerabilities and Technology
- Session 111: The Social Organization of Medical Violence
- Session 112: Imagining, Building and Sustaining Alternative Forms of Justice
- Session 114: Repertoires of Violence: Countermovement, Repression, Oppression, and Social Control
- Session 115: State and Interpersonal Violence against Contemporary Family Structures

SPECIAL SESSIONS

FRIDAY, AUGUST 9

12:30pm-2:10pm

- Session 011: Networking and Navigating at SSSP: Getting the Most Out of Conference Attendance

2:30pm-4:10pm

- Session 020: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Agenda for Social Justice: Active Agents for the Future

SATURDAY, AUGUST 10

8:30am-10:10am

- Session 038: Beyond Outrage, What Do We Do Now? Peace, Reconciliation, and Global Conflict
- Session 039: How to Get Published: Learning the Language of Academic Writing
- Session 043: Making the Most of Mentoring Opportunities

12:30pm-2:10pm

- Session 021: CRITICAL DIALOGUE: Sociology on the Ropes: Recent Attacks on the Discipline
- Session 058: Publishing Tips from the Editors of *Social Problems*

2:30pm-4:10pm

- Session 068: On the Market: Strategies for Landing a Job
- Session 072: Author Meets Critics: *Murder Town, USA: Homicide, Structural Violence, and Activism in Wilmington* by Yasser Arafat Payne, Brooklyn K. Hitchens, & Darryl L. Chambers, Rutgers University Press, 2023

SUNDAY, AUGUST 11

8:30am-10:10am

- Session 082: GIFTS: Good Ideas for Teaching Sociology and Publishing in TRAILS

12:00pm-1:30pm

- Session 116: Life in Sociology Lecture: Born a Sociologist by Dr. Barbara Katz Rothman

Committee and Divisional Meetings

<u>Committee Meetings</u>	<u>Day</u>	<u>Time</u>	<u>Location</u>
Accessibility Committee, 2023-24			Virtual
Annual Review Committee of the Executive Officer, 2023-24	Saturday	10:30 AM - 12:10 PM	Salon 6
Anti-Harassment Committee, 2023-24	Saturday	8:30 AM - 10:10 AM	Kafka
Arlene Kaplan Daniels Paper Award Committee, 2023-24			Virtual
Board of Directors Meeting I, 2023-24	Thursday	11:45 AM - 4:45 PM	Salon 1
Board of Directors Meeting II, 2023-24	Friday	4:15 PM - 6:15 PM	Salon 1
Board of Directors Meeting, 2024-25	Sunday	8:00 AM - 12:00 PM	Salon 1
Budget, Finance, and Audit Committee, 2023-24			Virtual
Budget, Finance, and Audit Committee, 2024-25			Virtual
Committee on Mentorship, 2023-24			Virtual
Council of Division Chairpersons and Program Co-Chairs, 2024-25	Sunday	2:30 PM - 4:10 PM	Salon 1
Council of Division Chairpersons, 2023-24	Friday	2:30 PM - 4:10 PM	Salon 1
Council of Division Chairpersons, 2023-24 & 2024-25	Friday	8:30 AM - 10:10 AM	Salon 1
Editorial and Publications Committee 2023-24 & 2024-25			Virtual
Feminist Collective Meeting	Friday	4:00 PM - 6:00 PM	Ballroom Centre
Joseph B. Gittler Award Committee, 2023-24	Friday	12:30 PM - 2:10 PM	Salon 4
Justice 21 Committee, 2023-24			Virtual
Kathleen S. Lowney Mentoring Award Committee, 2023-24			Virtual
Kauffman Foundation Paper Awards Committee, 2023-24			Virtual
Lee Scholar Support Fund Committee, 2023-24			Virtual
Lee Student Support Fund Committee, 2023-24			Virtual
Meeting to Discuss the 2028 Annual Meeting, 2023-24			Virtual
Membership and Outreach Committee, 2023-24 & 2024-25	Saturday	10:30 AM - 12:10 PM	Kafka
Nominations Committee, 2023-24 (Closed Meeting)			Virtual
Permanent Organization and Strategic Planning Committee, 2023-24 & 2024-25	Friday	2:30 PM - 4:10 PM	Salon 4
Program Chair(s), 2024-25 Meeting with the President, Administrative Officer, and IT Specialist			Virtual
Racial/Ethnic Minority Graduate Fellowship Committee, 2023-24			Virtual
SSSP Business Meeting	Friday	10:30 AM - 12:10 PM	Ballroom Centre
Student Meeting with Student Board Representatives, 2023-24			Virtual
Thomas C. Hood Social Action Award Committee, 2023-24			Virtual
Transnational Initiatives Committee, 2023-24			Virtual

The following committees will not meet because they have completed their work and/or do not have anything on their agenda to warrant meeting.

C. Wright Mills Award Committee
 Committee on Committees
 Committee on Social Action
 Doris Wilkinson Faculty Leadership Award Committee
 Erwin O. Smigel Award Committee

Lee Founders Award Committee
 Local Arrangements Committee
 Program Chair(s) Committee

Divisional Meetings

	<u>Day</u>	<u>Time</u>	<u>Location</u>
Community Research and Development	Friday	12:30 PM - 2:10 PM	Ballroom West
Conflict, Social Action, and Change	Saturday	10:30 AM - 12:10 PM	Ballroom West
Crime and Justice	Friday	4:30 PM - 6:10 PM	Ballroom West
Critical Race and Ethnic Studies			Virtual
Disability			Virtual
Drinking and Drugs			Virtual
Educational Problems			Virtual
Environment and Technology	Friday	12:30 PM - 2:10 PM	Ballroom West
Family	Saturday	10:30 AM - 12:10 PM	Ballroom West
Gender			Virtual
Global			Virtual
Health, Health Policy, and Health Services	Friday	4:30 PM - 6:10 PM	Ballroom West
Institutional Ethnography	Friday	12:30 PM - 2:10 PM	Salon 1
Labor Studies	Friday	4:30 PM - 6:10 PM	Ballroom West
Law and Society			Virtual
Poverty, Class, and Inequality			Virtual
Sexual Behavior, Politics, and Communities	Saturday	10:30 AM - 12:10 PM	Ballroom West
Social Problems Theory	Friday	4:30 PM - 6:10 PM	Ballroom West
Society and Mental Health			Virtual
Sociology and Social Welfare			Virtual
Sport, Leisure, and the Body			Virtual
Teaching Social Problems			Virtual
Youth, Aging, and the Life Course	Friday	12:30 PM - 2:10 PM	Ballroom West

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